

FuturHist

Barrier analysis: Identifying views on hindrances to the retrofitting of historic buildings

Project Overview

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Executive Summary

As part of the "Drawing the baseline" FuturHist work package, this report presents the results of Task 1.1 focused on the identification of barriers. A survey was conducted to assess the main barriers to energy efficiency in historic buildings. Feedback was gathered from various types of stakeholders engaged with energy retrofitting of historic buildings: practitioners, building owners, and public authorities. Almost 150 survey responses were collected from 25 different countries across Europe. Analysis of the data shows several trends within different stakeholder sectors and regions.

Additional in-depth feedback was received through a structured interview process and "practitioner form" targeting key individuals from the demo case countries. Twenty-five respondents from Spain, Sweden, Poland, and the United Kingdom were interviewed, while six individuals were selected to complete the "practitioner form."

A major barrier identified by most respondents to the survey and interviews was the current state of policies and legislation. In particular, current policies and legislation regarding energy efficiency are created with new construction in mind and significantly disadvantage historic buildings. Building performance targets are not always applicable for historic buildings, yet they are still largely obligated to adhere to them. Shortcomings in funding, awareness, traditional skills, and a lack of best-practice examples are also identified as significant barriers.

The "practitioner forms" showed that while there are clear national and international guidelines and standards for practitioners to perform heritage value assessments and energy value assessments, these require some refinement to address issues with applicability and complexity.

Of primary importance in addressing these barriers is a more nuanced approach in policy and legislation that better takes into account the unique conditions and requirements of historic buildings as well as the local contexts of the countries they are found. This could either mean a new set of policies specifically designed for - and only applicable to - historic buildings; or a reworking of existing legislation to better accommodate their realities.

The best solutions would take a holistic approach and address as much as possible all notable concerns voiced by the stakeholder respondents; improving resources for training, funding, and awareness raising to improve public opinion around the inherent sustainability and energy efficiency of historic buildings. By making progress across these areas, the overall situation for energy retrofits of historic buildings would be greatly improved.

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Table of Contents

Contents

Abbreviations and definitions	6
Introduction.....	7
1. Methodology	9
1.1. Survey.....	9
1.2. Structured Interviews Methodology	10
1.3. Practitioner Forms Methodology	12
2. Data Analysis – Key Findings.....	14
2.1. Survey and Interviews	14
2.2. Practitioner Forms	37
2.3. Interpretation of results.....	43
3. Conclusions and Outlook	46
4. References	48
5. Annexes.....	49
Annex 1 - WP1 FuturHist Barrier Survey – Original Survey Form.....	49
Annex 2 - WP1 Survey – Anonymised Raw Survey Data.....	56
Annex 3 – WP1 Interviews – Complete List of Interview Questions	74
Annex 4 - WP1 Interviews - Practitioner form	76
Annex 5 - WP1 Interviews – Detailed analysis of feedback provided through practitioner forms.....	77

Abbreviations and definitions

Barriers	Refers to any obstacle or challenge that inhibits the implementation or widespread adoption of energy-efficient technologies, practices, or policies in practice
Energy retrofit	A general concept for all types of renovations where reduced energy consumption is the main goal for the renovation. It is used for the entire renovation process, from planning to evaluation, and is closely related to sustainable renovation (Thuvander et al., 2012). Sustainable renovation of existing buildings is a way of extending the lifespan of a building and improving its living and working conditions, which includes lowering the energy used for those purposes (Asdrubali and Desideri, 2018, chapter 9)
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
Historic building or Building of heritage significance	Includes also buildings that are not statutorily designated as cultural heritage ("i.e. listed buildings").
HIBERAtlas	Historic Building Energy Retrofit Atlas
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
Likert scale	A rating scale used to measure survey participants' opinions and attitudes. Respondents specify their level of agreement or disagreement on a symmetric agree-disagree scale
Planning process	The process of identifying the need for energy performance improvements and defining appropriate improvement measures that match the requirements for the building in question. It would cover all the steps of the proposal procedure of EN 16883 (from the client's intentions to the final decision), but not the implementation, monitoring or maintenance of the intervention afterwards.
Step	Most important technical/practical aspects or considerations associated with the energy retrofit process of historic buildings (pre-design, design and post construction phases). Steps are not necessary implemented sequentially; some can be implemented in parallel during the retrofit process.
WP	Work Package

Introduction

FuturHist aims to develop replicable retrofit solutions for historic buildings of the future. Before any guidelines or solutions can be presented, it is first necessary to develop a better understanding of the challenges and obstacles faced by the different stakeholders involved in the retrofit of historic buildings. Recent research has shown that while there are many resources, recommendations, and options available relating to energy retrofits, building owners especially are hindered by a surplus of information and the gaps present between national initiatives and local realities. Understanding barriers as identified by stakeholder groups is a vital step in addressing a meaningful way forward. To that end, practitioners, heritage specialists, architects, researchers, engineers, building managers, owners, and others were invited to participate in the FuturHist Barriers Survey, with the aim of answering the main question “What do you think are the main barriers to making historic buildings more energy efficient?” Interviews were carried out in parallel with representatives of each target group along with a “practitioner form” for professionals involved in the design of retrofit projects to capture additional information.

The approach was adjusted to cover all target groups with a single survey as opposed to numerous specific surveys aimed at numerous specific groups. Not only is this adjustment less labour intensive, but it also provides more certainty in terms of the number of respondents and general outreach. Data collection was thus aided, and a general overview was obtained alongside targeted specific data-points. The parallel interview process targeted key individuals from four groups: Practitioners, Public Authorities, Professional Owners, and Private Owners. An additional “practitioner form” was created to collect further data on standards, guidelines and tool usage at different stages of the retrofit process, specifically by practitioners. Doing so refined the project’s understanding of the needs and challenges of practitioners, providing direct assistance to Work Package 4 “Development of an integrated planning toolkit” and Work Package 6 “Scale-up” and its Task 6.2 “Policy-making: Heritage authorities knowledge transfer”.

The results presented in this report are useful for successive stages of the FuturHist project. The identification of different types of barriers is crucial for:

1. The design of the FuturHist Toolkit (Work Package 4). Ensuring that the Toolkit is designed to address the main identified barriers for different potential user groups.
2. Informing the selection of Key Performance Indicators (Task 1.6). Ensuring that the selection of KPI:s is based on what is considered relevant by stakeholders, and that the indicators and assessment methods have the right level of complexity.
3. Facilitating the upscaling of the FuturHist methodology (Work Package 5). By focusing on main, transnational, barriers the FuturHist methodology will be well prepared for upscaling across borders in Europe.
4. The identification of policy proposals to address some of these barriers (Work Package 6 and its Task 6.2) that will be then disseminated amongst heritage authorities from European countries.

This document presents the results of the survey, interviews and the “practitioner forms”, interpreting and categorizing the data for better clarity and understanding.

The document is structured as follows:

1. Methodology

2. Data Analysis - Key Findings
3. Conclusions and Outlook
4. References
5. Annexes

1. Methodology

1.1. Survey

1.1.1. Structure of the Survey

The survey was divided into three sections (See *Annex 1*). The first section established the demographics of respondents, their professional background and expertise, their affiliation and membership of the International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS) and FuturHist, as well as where they are based. The second part, the survey's core, consisted of a series of questions to establish the current situation for professionals involved in the management and maintenance of historic buildings. Respondents were asked several open-ended questions along with a series of Likert-type scale questions in order to understand their perspective on the current state of retrofitting of historic buildings.

Within the context of the survey, the term "historic buildings" is used to include all buildings with heritage values, both listed and non-listed; while retrofit or retrofitting refers to energy retrofitting and similar interventions focusing on improved energy efficiency and sustainability. Other types of retrofit are not within the scope of this project.

1.1.2. Survey Distribution

The survey was intended to reach the three main target groups (stakeholder groups) defined by the FuturHist consortium:

- Practitioners
- Building owners
- Public authorities (including managers of public buildings, planning officers and heritage authorities)

These target groups should make it possible to obtain as differentiated a picture as possible of the current problems, especially as it can be assumed that there are different focal points depending on the group. This should be analysed in the survey.

The survey was distributed internally within the FuturHist consortium so that the extensive networks of the participants could be utilised to increase the reach. At the same time, ICOMOS utilised its wide membership list by sending the survey to the individual European National Committees and all members via the existing newsletter. Relevant ICOMOS working groups (e.g., the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive working group) were also directly informed about the survey. In addition, the survey was shared on social media and in the FuturHist project newsletter. In a second step, invitations to take part in the survey were resent to countries that were not represented in the responses after 10 days.

The survey received 148 answers from 25 countries, with respondents expressing their mainly professional opinions regarding the barriers to energy efficiency and retrofitting of historic buildings.

1.1.3. Limitations of the Survey

Given the limited number of survey responses compared to the actual number of professionals working in energy efficiency and retrofitting of European historic buildings, there are a few noticeable gaps in responses. Like any survey, it is important to acknowledge these limitations and keep them in mind when reviewing the data. Shortcomings are most noticeable in geographical terms. A few respondents' answers from outside Europe were disregarded in the data, but chiefly there are only a limited number of responses from eastern European countries. Furthermore, because only one or two responses were received from some countries, it is difficult to reach any firm conclusions about the situation there with such limited data points. It is also important to acknowledge that answers from respondents may not all be factual, but instead represent their perceptions and opinions. Nevertheless, the data is valuable for establishing an overall view of the broader situation, with clearly identifiable trends among different cohorts.

Since the structure of the survey questions primarily focused on the professional background and experience of respondents, building owners were not represented as a clear discreet grouping. However, the opinions and perspectives of owners of historic buildings were presented in two different ways. Firstly, the survey heard from numerous professionals working for municipal and regional governments who are the public owners of large collections of historic buildings. As representatives of these institutions, their professional work and experience relate directly to the realities of historic building ownership. This is especially relevant in the European context where public ownership of historic buildings is common. Secondly, professionals whose clients are owners of historic buildings (i.e. architects, engineers, etc.) reported opinions and concerns expressed to them by their clients throughout their careers. This latter information represents a valuable expression of public opinion, being as it is distilled by professional expertise. Furthermore, barriers that cannot be addressed solely by professionals working for their client-owners are precisely the most relevant to be addressed by any solutions proposed in the future.

1.2. Structured Interviews Methodology

1.2.1. Selection of Interview Respondents

Shortcomings in the survey data were supplemented by in-depth structured interviews carried out in parallel. The approach was adjusted from the original plan of conducting interviews as a follow-up to the survey, to carrying out the interviews in parallel with the survey process. The structured interview approach gathered insights from stakeholders involved in the planning process of retrofitting historic buildings. Interview participants were recruited based on two criteria: their involvement in the project's demo cases and the project partners' knowledge of individuals likely to provide valuable insights. This purposive sampling method ensured that the interviewees were well-positioned to provide meaningful information related to the study's objectives.

The interviews were conducted either face-to-face or online, depending on logistical constraints and the preferences of interviewees. Each participant provided standard consent to allow the use of the data collected during the interviews. The interview process began with an introduction to the FuturHist project and an explanation of the interview's purpose, alongside a clarification of key terms to ensure consistency in understanding.

1.2.2. Structure of Interviews

A structured set of questions was prepared for each stakeholder group, with some overlap across groups to enable comparison (see *Annex 3* for a list of all the interview questions). All interviews in WP1 were made with the same interview template containing questions from different tasks, see deliverable D1.3. The questions were designed to elicit specific insights from each target group's perspective while maintaining the flexibility to explore broader themes. The interviewer was encouraged to use prompts such as "interesting, tell me more", "how do you mean?", "explain further", "please elaborate" when appropriate to capture more in-depth responses. Interviews lasted between 30-90 minutes, depending on the interviewee's availability and the depth of discussion.

The interviews were conducted in the local language, recorded, and later transcribed for analysis. Transcriptions were translated into English, with minor edits to improve clarity without altering meaning. All transcripts were anonymised. This structured and methodical approach allowed for comprehensive data collection, ensuring that the perspectives of different stakeholder groups were systematically documented for subsequent analysis.

1.2.3. Overview of Respondents

In total, 25 respondents from Spain, Sweden, Poland and the United Kingdom were interviewed.

No	ID	Stakeholder group	Country	Role
1	PRAPL1	Practitioner	Poland	Designer (architect)
2	PRAPL2	Practitioner	Poland	Architect
3	PRAES1	Practitioner	Spain	Engineer
4	PRAES2	Practitioner	Spain	Architect
5	PRAES3	Practitioner	Spain	Architect
6	PRAES4	Practitioner	Spain	Researcher (architect)
7	PRASE1	Practitioner	Sweden	Heritage expert at architectural firm
8	PRASE2	Practitioner	Sweden	Heritage expert at architectural firm
9	PRAUK1	Practitioner	UK	Designer (architect)
10	PUBPL1	Public Authority	Poland	Planner at heritage authority (architect)
11	PUBPL2	Public Authority	Poland	Administrative official at heritage authority
12	PUBPL3	Public Authority	Poland	Regional conservator at heritage authority
13	PUBPL4	Public Authority	Poland	Regional conservator at heritage authority
14	PUBES1	Public Authority	Spain	Heritage expert
15	PUBES2	Public Authority	Spain	Planner
16	PUBES3	Public Authority	Spain	Officer at heritage authority
17	PUBES1	Public Authority	Sweden	Heritage expert at national heritage authority body
18	PUBUK1	Public Authority	UK	Policy and Strategy Manager

19	PROPL1	Professional Owner	Poland	Property manager
20	PROPL2	Professional Owner	Poland	Deputy head of real estate company
21	PROUK1	Professional Owner	UK	CEO of social housing organisation
22	PRIPL1	Private Owner	Poland	Building owner
23	PRISE1	Private Owner	Sweden	Building owner
24	PRIUK1	Private Owner	UK	Owning a flat in a listed building
25	PRIUK2	Private Owner	UK	Owning a flat in a listed building

Table 1. Overview of interviewees located in the four demo countries

1.3. Practitioner Forms Methodology

Practitioners, those construction professionals directly involved in retrofit projects of historic buildings (e.g. architects), were asked to fill a specific ‘practitioner form’ in when they took part in the in-depth structured interviews.

The form aimed to list the guidelines/standards and tools (e.g. software) used by practitioners for each of the main “steps” of any retrofit project – considering the pre-design, design and post construction phases. 7 “steps” were identified before the interview process by project partners involved in Work Package 1 based on the “assessment categories” from the European guidelines for improving the energy performance of historic buildings EN 16883. These 7 “steps” represent the most important technical/practical aspects or considerations associated with the energy retrofit of historic buildings:

- Heritage value assessment
- Assessment of the use of the building
- Condition survey and technical documentation
- Energy performance assessment
- Indoor environmental assessment
- Economic viability (e.g. Life cycle costing)
- Environmental impact (e.g. Life cycle assessment, waste)

It is important to note that the “steps” are not necessary implemented sequentially; some can be implemented in parallel during the retrofit process.

Respondents were also asked to indicate when these guidelines/standards and tools were used in the retrofit process - when the “step” was meant to take place - and what the related advantages and disadvantages (“pros and cons”) were when using them.

The template of the practitioner form can be found in *Annex 4*. The table below indicates the number of interviews with/forms filled in by practitioners across the four demonstration site countries:

	Spain	Poland	Sweden	UK	Total
No. interviews	4	2	1	1	8
No. forms filled in	3	1	1	1	6

Table 2. Number of interviews of practitioners and forms filled in per country

Data from all the forms was compiled in one Excel spreadsheet to form a dataset. This enabled the proper analysis of this data: comparing responses, identifying and compiling similarities and divergences and identifying main trends. Key findings were produced as a result of this analysis, for each “step” and the overall retrofit process – to understand more generally what works or does not work for practitioners in terms of guidelines/standards and tools used to support the retrofit process for historic buildings. Data collected will provide inputs to WP4 and help inform the development of FuturHist’s approach to retrofitting historic and the associated toolkit.

2. Data Analysis – Key Findings

2.1. Survey and Interviews

The results provide a clear picture of the barriers and challenges faced by European professionals in energy retrofitting of historic buildings. Survey responses and perspectives were wide and varied, with 148 respondents from 25 countries, but noticeably, several concerns and frustrations were repeatedly recorded across the results.

2.1.1. Demographics

Regional Demographics

Survey responses were received from individuals from 25 European countries [see *Figure 1*]. While significant gaps still remain, the survey results represent a broad geographical spectrum across the continent. The wide variety of countries represented enables the identification of trends based not only on individual countries of origin, but across wider regions. A few responses were also received from outside Europe; three from the United States of America, two from Canada, one from Argentina, and one respondent in South Africa but working in Ireland. As the scope of the project is limited to Europe, these responses, with the exception of the respondent working in Ireland, were not taken into consideration in the final data analysis.

Figure 1 Countries represented in the survey

Figure 2 Location of respondents

A significant percentage of respondents are from a small number of countries; the United Kingdom is the most represented country with 37 respondents, followed by Italy with 22 [see Figure 2]. However, the majority of countries listed have responses from multiple individuals, while a small number of countries are represented by only 1 or 2 respondents each. In most cases, responses are dispersed evenly across the majority of countries. [see Figure 2a].

In which country are you based?

Figure 2a Respondents by country

Taking into account the number of responses and their geographical distribution, it is possible to categorize responses by region or sub-region. For the purpose of this document, three regional categories are established: Northern Europe (64 respondents), Central Europe (42 respondents), and Southern Europe (42 respondents) [see *Figure 3*]. While these three groupings may seem to incorporate countries with very different cultural or historical contexts, the primary focus is on shared climactic conditions, typologies, and needs in retrofitting buildings for improved energy efficiency. From the demo case countries, there were 37 respondents from the UK, seven from Poland, six from Sweden, and four from Spain. Together, these results represent roughly 36% of total respondents, thus it is clear that respondents were not limited to the case study countries alone, but in fact the majority are from other countries, offering a much wider view of the current situation across the continent.

Figure 3 Geographical regions

Greater specificity and more distinct regional groupings can potentially be made at a later stage with increased inputs. However, due to the limited number of responses from certain countries, a higher number of groups with fewer countries in each would not be practical at this stage, nor would it assist in visualizing or understanding the data collected.

What is your profession?

Figure 4 A breakdown of every profession recorded.

The graphic is intended for illustrative purposes only, showing the diversity of professions among respondents. For the complete list of careers, please consult the accompanying anonymised survey [Annex 2].

Professional Demographics

Survey respondents were asked to state their profession. By its open-ended nature, the question “What is your profession?” unsurprisingly resulted in a wide variety of answers, with only a few given answers having been repeated [see figure 4]. The most notable examples of this are “architect”, “researcher”, and “engineer.” Using these answers, survey respondents were grouped into six professional profiles: Architecture and Design; Academia and Research; Engineering, Construction, and Field Practitioners; Site or Project Management; and Other. The professional profiles of survey respondents are wide and varied. The results are reflective of the diverse careers involved in the complexities of energy retrofitting of historic buildings. Survey respondents have experience in theoretical research, hands-on site construction, policy and decision making, ownership of historic buildings, and many other things.

The respondents were also categorised into three major stakeholder groups: Practitioners, Owners and Public Authorities. As there were also a substantial number of respondents from academic backgrounds, a fourth group of “academia” was added. It is important to bear in mind that it is frequently possible for professionals working in the sector to be categorised as belonging to multiple stakeholder groups. For example, a university professor that has a professional practice as an architect, and is simultaneously the owner of an historic building.

	Survey	Interviews
Practitioners	71	9
Owners	8	7
Public Authorities	19	9
Academia	46	0
N/A	4	0

Table 3. Number of respondents from each stakeholder group for the survey and for the interviews

Professional Memberships

The overwhelming majority of survey respondents are not currently members of FuturHist [see *Table 4*]. This suggests that the survey reached professionals not previously engaged with FuturHist research efforts and projects. It also suggests that the responses are from a broader range of professionals than have been previously contacted in FuturHist efforts. Membership of ICOMOS was better represented in responses when compared to FuturHist memberships [see *Table 4*]. Nevertheless, a significant majority (roughly 69%) of survey respondents are not current members of ICOMOS either. Taken together, these two facts suggest that the survey reached new audiences and the opinions expressed by respondents are representative of a wide range of professionals. Even if the professional networks of the two organisations were used in distribution, the majority of respondents come from outside the membership body of each.

	Yes	No
Are you a member of FuturHist?	16 (10.8%)	132 (89.2%)
Are you a member of ICOMOS?	46 (31.1%)	102 (68.9%)

Table 4. FuturHist and ICOMOS memberships

2.1.2. Identification of Main Barriers

There is no well-established taxonomy of barriers for energy retrofit of historic buildings. Instead of eliciting opinions about a predetermined set of barrier categories, the study has used an inductive approach with the aim to establish the most important barriers and categories. Using predetermined categories (e.g. economic barriers, regulatory barriers etc) could point respondents in a certain direction, leading to biased results. Therefore, we used the open question “What do you think are the main barriers to making historic buildings more energy efficient?” This question was used both in the survey and the interviews, generating a rich dataset. Follow-up questions based on predetermined categories were used in the interviews in order to get comprehensive answers.

The main question of the survey “*What do you think are the main barriers to making historic buildings more energy efficient?*” allowed respondents to voice their professional opinions regarding the current state of affairs regarding retrofit of historic buildings. The question was intentionally broad in order to not introduce bias (e.g. by presenting a predetermined categorisation of barriers). The same question was also used for all the interviews and the interview answers have complemented the survey results.

There was a possibility for respondents to answer with multiple barriers. One can assume that those answering with more than one barrier would put them in descending order of priority, but this has not been analyzed. All mentioned barriers have been assigned equal weight. The answers were labelled and put into categories. Categorisation was made with an inductive approach based on the content of the individual barrier labels. In total there were 260 single barriers grouped into six categories. Seven additional answers were not included in the categorization as they were assessed as non-applicable.

Overall barrier categorization

Across all stakeholder groups, professional profiles and regions there was a general consensus that a number of elements or conditions are lacking. Respondents frequently mentioned the lack of public support, awareness, funding, understanding and experience, time, adequate materials and products, and skilled and trained craftspeople. The financial and regulatory barriers are dominating, but the variety of identified barriers is quite large. It is also the case that many barriers, also across categories, are intertwined. This shows the complexity of the task and the many facets of the renovation process.

Figure 5. Overall barrier categorization, 260 answers to the question “What do you think are the main barriers to making historic buildings more energy efficient?” were categorised into six barrier categories.

Figure 5 shows the six barrier categories that were identified based on a total of 260 answers to the question “What do you think are the main barriers to making historic buildings more energy efficient?” There is an overlap between barrier categories and it is not always easy to identify if a barrier belongs to a certain category or not.

Financial and regulatory barriers were the most frequent ones, followed by awareness and mindset, technical barriers, knowledge and skills gap, and finally planning related barriers. 3 % of the barriers could not be categorized.

A Scottish architect working as a retrofit designer (PRAUK1) gives some insight in how barriers can be connected. This architect suggests that conservation restrictions on most listed buildings prohibits external façade insulation and goes on to discuss how internal insulation is a viable alternative (mentioning that technical pitfalls have to be considered). Furthermore, the added insulation takes up valuable dwelling space. Another option discussed to decarbonise buildings is the installation of heat pumps, but here there are challenges related to the heating infrastructure and the process of transitioning to a communal heating system. Clients, according to the experience of this practitioner, prefer individual heating systems, and it is difficult to coordinate when there are many owners. Also, less affluent groups can have difficulties accommodating the cost of a heat pump.

This practitioner’s experience shows that it is difficult to point out a single barrier as most important, but there is a mix of factors depending not only on the building construction or conservation protection, but also on ownership and communal infrastructure.

“It’s slightly trickier thing with social housing, where I think that it all [installing heat pumps] works quite nicely for people who can afford to pay for their heat. But we work a lot with social housing. That’s a kind of different landscape where you’ve got people who are choosing between heating and eating /.../ But we can’t push the fabric too hard, because otherwise we’re encroaching people’s dwelling

space. But also the client doesn't want communal heating system. They want individual heating systems” (PRAUK1)

Regulatory barriers

Figure 6. Regulatory barriers vs. Stakeholder group

Policy and regulatory barriers are the most frequently referenced, see figure 6. The most common one is that heritage protection limits intervention. One could ask if this should be considered a barrier at all, as it is a legal condition. However, other barriers mentioned give hints: “Unnecessarily complicated administrative processes”, “Contradicting policies”, “Lack of definition and criteria in policy”, “Too strict enforcing of heritage protection”, “Hesitation of conservation professionals.” These all point to there being something problematic with policies and their application which is not a criticism of heritage protection policy per se, but of its design and application.

Some interviewees were frustrated with the ambiguity related to planning permission, the slow process to get permission, and the dissonance from policymakers:

“what you can and can't do with these properties and what I guess you do need planning permission for and what you don't need planning permission for it. It it's not immediately transparent. And sometimes you've got to go through an engagement process with local authorities to unpick what's going to be acceptable. Which takes time. We're trying to accelerate everything. How do we shortcut that? I think that's an interesting question. Good guidance, clear guidance. If it's already there, it just needs to be put out there a bit more.” (PRAUK1)

“dissonance between the government saying there is a climate emergency and you've got to do something about it, and the constraints of planning regulation.” (PROUK1)

A more detailed discussion of policies in relation to energy retrofit of historic buildings can be found in deliverable 1.3 from the FuturHist project.

Another common concern voiced across regions and professional sectors is that current policy and regulations do not adequately take into consideration the unique nature and characteristics of historic

buildings. Legislation was frequently cited as a barrier rather than an aid to initiatives. To date, building legislation and regulations in individual European nation-states have focused on the construction of new structures and buildings. Historical building stock or conversions are not considered, leading to an objective that can often only be realised through major interventions in the substance. Historic building structures and their qualities are ignored.

Rather, there are separate laws or guidelines for the area of historic buildings, which refer to target values (energy-efficient refurbishment or corresponding specifications for U-values), but these are structured in such a way that they take into account the special qualifications and possibilities of a historic building typology.

While the current situation of legislation and policy is more directly covered and analysed in task 1.3, the main value presented in the survey results in regard to policy is the opportunity to build a picture of public opinion on the subject. While the answers respondents gave may not be factual, with misunderstandings, misinterpretations, and even ignorance of the actual policies in place, they do represent the professional opinions of those working in the field. Responses It is important to recognize this distinction; respondents' answers offer insight into commonly held opinions relating to policy and legislation that can often differ greatly from the actual policies themselves.

Financial barriers

Figure 7. Financial barriers vs. Stakeholder group

Financial barriers are the second most frequently referenced category [see *Figure 7*]. Concern was repeatedly stated in both the survey and interviews that a focus on short term investment costs of energy retrofits along with renovations was acting as a serious deterrent to building owners to take action, even if the retrofits would result in long term savings further down the line.

Respondents were asked a series of questions related to funding; whether funding was available for listed buildings, non-listed buildings, whether funding was available for maintenance and for repairs. When interpreting the responses, it is important to note that while respondents may state no funding is available, it is possible that individual respondents are simply not aware of available funding options and initiatives in their areas. If this is the case, this situation itself raises another concern: if funding is available, but the relevant professionals and building owners are not made aware of it properly, efficient use of funding could be severely hindered. In short, not only should funding be made available, but distributors of this funding (whether public or private) should make efforts to ensure the

relevant potential recipients of funding are aware of their options.

With this in mind, a review of respondents' answers shows that funding options and awareness of these options varies by profession and region. In Northern Europe, architects, engineers and field practitioners were more aware of funding options than other professional profiles in the region. In Central Europe, there were far more respondents aware of funding options and describing them in some detail. It is likely that in this region funding options are more numerous, or awareness of options is greater or a combination of the two. Significantly, in Southern Europe, there is less awareness of funding options. There were far more responses along the lines of "I don't know" or "I am not aware" than a more emphatic "no." This level of uncertainty suggests that whatever funding options are available are not being communicated properly to professionals in the region. Respondents' answers are more representative of public opinion than the actual situation. An expression of ignorance of funding availability does not mean the funding does not exist.

In the interviews it is stated that cost effective, standard solutions are impossible to use either because of heritage protection or because of technical compatibility (or both). A private owner in Scotland rates high costs as the biggest barrier, giving the example of replacing windows with replicas as a very costly option – but the only one that would be allowed by the conservation authorities.

"There are technical solutions within the regulations, but they are just very expensive." (PRIUK1)

Interview answers from a practitioner respondent and a public authority respondent shed light on what can be hidden behind the barrier "cost" that was a frequent answer in the survey. Their answers show that there is an interplay between a lack of economies of scale, lack of access to capital, and grant schemes that don't take into account the renovations of historic buildings:

"And at the moment, we're sort of in the early adopter stage. It's quite additionally expensive. So there's a premium. You know, if you were to go and do this, there would be there's a premium on your expenditure. Because these things tend to be not necessarily bespoke, but there aren't the economies of scale yet that drives down the cost of these innovative solutions. And so I think that is prohibiting or at least limiting organisations, institutions and individuals from attempting retrofit of their buildings." (PROUK1)

"...current grant funding is also potentially a bit of a straitjacket for certain property owners. You can get a grant for doing a suite of measures, but if you're wanting to take a whole building approach and you can't do the windows as part of that suite of measures, that's a blocker. /.../ I just can't help but feel like if there's going to be money made available for a project, it should just be made available for a project to do all of the stuff that needs to be done on that project. /.../ it should be flexible based on the onus of the design team and the client and what's right for the project." (PRAUK1)

The cost-effectiveness of energy retrofit measures was discussed by several of the Polish respondents. One practitioner had concerns that there are weak incentives for home owners and that they think it is too costly.

"People are reluctant to retrofit HBs because they think it is very costly. Retrofits themselves are perceived as something positive, but the costs, especially shock costs, are a major barrier." (PRAPL2)

The answer from one professional owner shows that interpreting cost as a barrier can be misleading, as he/she specifically refers to a lack of cost-effective solutions and that thermal retrofits are economically sound from the outset:

"Technology is a major obstacle, as in HBs it is not possible to use standard, cheap solutions. The lack of cost-effective, proven solutions that would be acceptable to conservation services is a major obstacle. /.../ I do not think there are any economic barriers as thermal retrofits are economically sound. /.../ There are not enough funds to sufficiently retrofit buildings." (PROPL2)

Also adding to the ambiguity in how answers could be interpreted is the answer from a Spanish

interviewee:

“My experience is that we have funding available, but we are not able to manage it because we lack staff or we lack training in the field. For instance, there is a kind of caution not to get involved in a project with European funding. So I honestly believe that right now the problem is not one of financial availability.” (PUBES1)

Awareness and mindset

Figure 8. Barriers related to awareness and mindset vs. Stakeholder group

Figure 8 shows the different barriers categorized as “awareness and mindset”. This category includes barriers originating in the lack of awareness of both individuals and organisations. The most common one, across stakeholder groups, is the lack of awareness about the special needs of historic buildings, i.e. that both professionals and owners are unaware that historic buildings need special treatment because of their technical construction and/or heritage significance. The category covers barriers related to awareness and mindset of different stakeholder groups, but also more overarching ones such as “orientation of sector on new construction”.

Technical barriers

Figure 9. Technical barriers vs. Stakeholder group

The technical barriers are shown in figure 9. The most common technical barrier for all stakeholder groups except owners is “Traditional constructions require non-standard solutions”. This might not be a barrier by itself; more a matter of fact. However, interview answers hint that there is a perceived potential for the development of innovative, robust and cost-effective solutions also for traditional constructions, but that this potential is not realised due to a focus of the construction sector on new construction, and a lack of expertise of the building physics of traditional buildings:

“I do not see any technical barriers arising from technology itself. There are certain barriers that stem from a historical building's specificity in terms of building physics. For instance, a 19th century fort, which is damp and cold and has immense thermal mass that makes it difficult to heat and thus difficult to retrofit. Current technologies are at their core designed with new buildings in mind, and historical buildings are sometimes too different from them. From this standpoint, I believe building physics expertise is a key obstacle.” (PRAPL2)

Two technical barriers were emphasized by building owners: “Loss of living surface in small dwellings” (due to insulation, boiler space etc), and “Disruptance to occupants during the implementation phase”. These barriers can be quite important from a building owner’s perspective but are likely rarely in focus for other professional groups.

Knowledge and skills gap

Figure 10. Barriers related to knowledge and skills gap vs. Stakeholder group

The Swedish National heritage board conducted a study in 2010 with practitioners in the heritage sector to map the need for knowledge about energy efficiency in historic buildings. Not surprisingly, all respondents called for more knowledge. However when exemplifying this, they all pointed to a lack of availability of existing knowledge. They asked for streamlined accessible information, knowledge repositories, forums, independent consultants, handbooks, good examples, seminars etc. (Altahr-Cederberg et al. 2010). A recent UK study came to a similar result that the problem (of making historic buildings more energy efficient) was not a lack of knowledge, but a lack of knowledge utilization: “the main hurdle seemed to be disseminating this [expertise] more widely.” (Marie Stuart 2014, p. 190).

Respondents were asked if they were aware of a “best practice database for energy retrofit of historic buildings.” Apart from individual highly localized or regional examples like DuMo-Prestatiekaart in the

Netherlands, or Historic Scotland within the UK, respondents typically gave one of two answers: either that they were not aware of any, or they gave the example of the Historic Building Energy Retrofit Atlas (HiBERAtlas). Apart from this example, there was no other single centralized database referenced. A few respondents referenced databases that are no longer current, active, or even accessible, like Periscope. Interestingly, judging by the survey responses, the HiBERAtlas is proportionally better known in Central and Southern Europe compared to Northern Europe.

Planning related

Figure 11. Planning related barriers Observations by Stakeholder Group

Planning related barriers are shown in figure 11. Also in this category there is a rather wide spread of barriers, some related to the process (e.g. “Lack of interdisciplinary planning”), and some related to the lack of focus on specific aspects (e.g. “Heritage values are not identified”, “Not taking into account embedded energy”). Notably, the owner group identified “Difficult to coordinate multiple ownership” as a common barrier.

2.1.3. Observations by Region

While concerns about the shortcomings of policy and legislation were universally voiced in some form, this particular concern was especially emphasized by respondents in Northern Europe in the open form text questions of the survey. They were far more likely to identify policy and legislation as a principal barrier to retrofitting of historic buildings. Policies designed for new construction being poorly adapted to historic buildings, and a lack of knowledge and understanding of the specific needs of historic buildings were frequently referenced. However, for the Likert-scale question “Do policies regarding renovation of historic buildings support the planning of energy retrofits in an effective way?” negative responses (answers of 1 or 2 on the 1-5 scale) across the regions were more evenly distributed. 51.6% of respondents in Northern Europe answered in the negative, compared to 57.1% in Central Europe and 66.7% in Southern Europe. This shows a discrepancy between the qualitative

and quantitative format answers that was further explored in the structured interviews.

Conversely, in Southern Europe, especially in Italy, there was a noticeable focus on issues of aesthetics and a perceived reluctance and fear from policy and decision makers to allow for retrofits that might jeopardize the aesthetic qualities of a historic building. These frustrations were not voiced by the public authorities themselves, but rather by those in the architectural, engineering and field practitioner sectors. In their statements, respondents suggested that these concerns stem from a misunderstanding among policymakers that retrofitting threatens the historic and cultural value of building and that all retrofits inherently lessen the authenticity of historic buildings. Respondents also suggested that greater awareness and understanding was required to correct these misconceptions.

The expertise/skill among professionals involved in energy retrofits of historic buildings is sufficient

Figure 12. Expertise/skill among professionals per region

Are there generally enough good examples of energy retrofit in historic buildings?

Figure 13. Access to enough good examples per region

Do policies regarding renovation of historic buildings support the planning of energy retrofits in an effective way?

Figure 14. supporting policies per region

Is there sufficient publicly available support and guidance for the energy retrofit of historic buildings?

Figure 15. Access to publicly available support and guidance per region

2.1.4. Observations by Professional Profile

What is very clear when reviewing answers from respondents with different professional backgrounds is that each respondent approaches the subject differently based on their profession. As it may be expected, respondents working in academia and research were more likely to focus on theoretical issues, policy decisions, and overall approaches to retrofitting historic buildings. Engineers and field practitioners focused more on details such as thermal barriers, thermal bridges, suitable window and door replacements, and specific issues directly relating to individual building projects. Professionals working in academia and to a lesser degree architecture are more aware of good examples and precedents of energy retrofits in historic buildings. Architecture professionals especially, and to a lesser extent engineers and field practitioners voiced concerns that policy and legislation can act as a barrier. Public authorities however are more divided on this matter. These differences also highlight the multidisciplinary and the great variety of professional profiles engaged in energy retrofits and management of historic buildings.

The expertise/skill among professionals involved in energy retrofits of historic buildings is sufficient

Figure 16. Expertise/skill among professionals

Are there generally enough good examples of energy retrofit in historic buildings?

Figure 17. Access to enough good examples per profession

Do policies regarding renovation of historic buildings support the planning of energy retrofits in an effective way?

Figure 18. supporting policies per profession

Is there sufficient publicly available support and guidance for the energy retrofit of historic buildings?

- Architecture and Design
- Academia and Research
- Engineering, Construction and Field Practitioners
- Policymakers and Heritage Professionals
- Site/Project Management
- Other

Figure 19. Access to publicly available support and guidance per profession

2.2. Practitioner Forms

2.2.1. Detailed analysis per “step”

This subsection details the findings drawn from the analysis of the practitioner's form data compiled in the dataset for each of the 7 “steps” of energy retrofit projects of historic buildings. It covers both general trends and specific qualitative data that were extracted from the dataset. The number of respondents is indicated for each “step”.

More detailed data resulting from the analysis of the dataset, and presented using tables based on the practitioner form template, can be found in *Annex 5* – including examples of tools.

Heritage value assessment (6 respondents)

There was a strong consensus amongst respondents that the step to perform a heritage value assessment is guided predominantly by national, and by international heritage conservation legislation/standards. Professional practice/processes/methods at national level to analyse historic significance were also mentioned. Their main advantages, as mentioned by respondents, were the accessibility of heritage conservation legislation/standards, the fact they form a well-integrated system, the fact there are international standards, and the clear legal framework. One respondent specifically mentioned, as an advantage, the fact that they ensure the protection of the character, appearance and aesthetic of heritage assets. The difficulty to adapt these heritage conservation legislation/standards to individual buildings was seen as a disadvantage, and it was mentioned by one respondent that they limit or prevent retrofit interventions, and that the documentation process is time-consuming.

When it comes to tools used to support the process, the respondents mentioned tasks to be performed rather than proper tools to be used – e.g. studying the history of the building and its context, carrying out a site visit and analysing the significance of the building. There was one exception regarding the tools used to create drawings (e.g. Polycam, Autocad). One respondent mentioned he did not use any tool. One respondent mentioned that there is no other way to fully understand a building and what it represents than using/performing the aforementioned tools and tasks.

There was clear feedback that this step should take place at the beginning of the retrofit process (either at pre-design stage or at the start of the design phase) and potentially at another point in time too, during the building permit stage (when a planning permission/listed building consent is sought from a city council or local authority).

Assessment of the use of the building (6 respondents)

There was potentially a problem with the wording of the question with regards to the meaning of “use of the building”, as one respondent said he was unsure if he understood the question. However, the analysis of the answers tends to provide reassurances that most respondents understood the question – some adopting a holistic approach to answering the assessment of use by considering structural survey to probably define what type of loads (applied to the building structure) and activities can be acceptable in a given historic building.

For respondents, the step to assess the use of historic buildings is guided predominantly by

construction and planning legislation/standards at national level, and to a lesser extent by heritage conservation standards at international and national level. It was felt that structural requirements are very well defined with a comprehensive approach. However, respondents highlighted the fact that there is uncertainty about the structural condition of historic buildings and limited flexibility to adapt them. Another issue regarding existing guidelines/standards was that existing legislation/standards are not very focused on use and space planning.

The tools mentioned by respondents to perform this step only focused on engagement with users – to understand users' needs/challenges and current use of the building and collect feedback. Respondents mentioned various tasks to be performed, without indicating the tools to do so – e.g. structural tests, site visit, gathering/analysing historical documentation on the building, and consultation, engagement events outside the building, door to door with residents, and resident meetings.

There was clear feedback that this step should take place at the beginning of the retrofit process (either at pre-design stage or at the start of the design phase).

Condition survey and technical documentation (4 respondents)

For respondents, the step to undertake a condition survey and gather technical documentation is guided by construction legislation/standards at national level and heritage conservation standards at international and national level. It was felt that there were detailed criteria provided by existing guidelines/standards (presumably heritage conservation standards at the national/international level). Additionally, it was also felt that legislation/standards do not provide specific guidance for any type of building – implying it is too general, which is seen as a problem. Furthermore, it was mentioned that up-to-date technical documentation of the buildings is often not available.

The tools mentioned by respondents to perform this step covered the collection of 2D/3D technical information and the processing/creation of 2D/3D technical information. It was mentioned that whilst these tools provide precise documentation on the current condition of the building, they are expensive. It was also felt that there was a lack of information about internal structure in the case of building pathology surveys. One respondent was not aware of any condition survey tool.

Respondents mentioned various tasks to be performed without indicating the tools to do so – carrying out a building pathology analysis (i.e. understanding damage to masonry, wooden elements, etc.), analysing the resistance of the building's structural elements (bearing walls, domes, etc.) and carrying out a historic analysis of the building.

There was clear feedback that this step should take place at the beginning of the retrofit process but diverging views on the specific point in time (either at the pre-design stage or at the start of the design phase or during the stage when a light touch design is being developed). It was also mentioned that the process should potentially take place at another point in time too, during the building permit stage (when a planning permission/listed building consent is sought from a city council or local authority).

Energy performance assessment (5 respondents)

There was a strong consensus amongst respondents that the step to assess the energy performance of historic buildings is guided by energy performance legislation for buildings at the European level (EPBD), energy performance legislation/standards for buildings at the national level and energy performance standards (non-governmental) for buildings at the national level. This is complemented by energy performance standards (non-governmental) for buildings at the international level and construction legislation/standards at the national level. The feedback received was very positive in that these guidelines/standards are very well-defined, detailed, provide clear targets, and there is

some flexibility in how some standards can be used (i.e. following the steps but not necessary the specific targets). However, complexity was pinpointed as the main issue: complexity of the standards/legislations themselves, an increasing complexity due to the large numbers of standards/legislation that can generate contradictions between each other (a suggestion was made to group them in one single standard/guideline), the fact that different procedures are required depending on the standards/tools being used, and the difficulty in applying the standards to historic buildings.

A lot of tools were mentioned to perform this step, and they can be split between those being compulsory or recognised by national governments to produce EPCs or required for energy modelling calculations, those who are not compulsory but are widely used and in-house tools. These tools include software programs for energy modelling that are compulsory at national level or recognised by governments, including Dynamic Simulation Modelling (software), and those that are non-obligatory. Other tools cover hygrothermal risk assessment (i.e. risk of condensation in walls, roofs, ground floors), thermal bridges, modelling heat fluxes through buildings components, thermal load and temperature and relative humidity evolution, U-value calculations – some of which can be covered by an energy modelling software. The combination of tools (software) to generate 3D model and to assign energy performance values to the walls, roof, floor, and an in-house tool to report on current energy performance of a given building were also mentioned. The feedback was extremely diverse and tended to be specific to the various tools used – see data from the relevant table in *Annex 5* for more detailed information. However, some general conclusions can be made: easiness to use the tool (e.g. when based on Excel like Passive House Planning Package) and provide results quickly are strong advantages, whilst the fact that a tool is very time consuming, requires skills and is slow to operate is problematic. Precision is very important and so is the ability to generate a lot of data that can be reused during the design process - whilst some tools can provide results that are not precise or are more focused on compliance with regulations (mandatory as part of national legislations) and there may be the need to use different tools. The possibility to use data from one tool to another is paramount, and so is the need for flexibility. The tool should allow comparisons between different retrofit scenarios to test them and facilitate data interpretation, as this part of the design phase is an iterative process required before defining the most appropriate technical solutions that will be implemented during the works. As such, the tools should facilitate this part of the design process and accelerate it – as it is, in essence, a rather time-consuming process. It was mentioned that whilst these tools are indispensable, they have their limitations. A well-designed monitoring campaign is absolutely necessary to calibrate and validate the energy models; otherwise, their results may not be reliable.

There was clear feedback that this step should take place at a more developed design stage or building permit stage. It was also mentioned that this step should happen at several design stages, to check the performance of the design, and that this step should also happen after completion of the project.

Indoor environmental assessment (5 respondents)

For respondents, the step to assess the indoor environment of historic buildings is guided by energy performance of buildings legislation/standards at national level, indoor air quality in buildings standards (non-governmental) at national level and construction legislation/standards at national level. Ad hoc approaches/outourced services to specialists and conservation guidelines were also mentioned. It was felt that the standards/guidelines were clear and that they provide a comprehensive approach. However, there was a consensus that the main challenge is complexity: complexity of the standards/legislations themselves, increasing complexity due to the large numbers of standards/legislation that can generate contradictions between each other, and difficulty in achieving

a compromise between comfort and protection of historic buildings.

To perform this step, the same tools (software programs) as for energy performance assessment were mentioned – some of which are integrated energy modelling software programs. The need for tools to perform microclimate measurements/building performance monitoring (temperature, humidity and carbon dioxide), multi-criteria certification and comfort levels assessment/thermal survey (thermal camera) was indicated by respondents. It was mentioned that these tools provide data for other assessments (e.g. Wufi for hygrothermal risk). But it was mentioned that there is always uncertainty in the results of these parameters associated with indoor environmental assessment due to the actual use/occupancy of the building once it is retrofitted.

Respondents mentioned tasks to be performed rather than proper tools to be used – carry out post occupancy evaluation, ask data from clients on operational parameters (e.g. energy use, temperature settings) and visit the property and interview residents or building owners.

There were various divergences in the feedback received as to when this step should take place - at the beginning of the retrofit process (at the start of the design phase), at a more developed design stage or building permit stage, or after completion of the works. It was also mentioned that this step could happen at several design stages - at the beginning of the retrofit process and after completion of the works.

Economic viability (e.g. Life cycle costing) - (5 respondents)

For respondents, the step to assess economic viability is guided by professional guidelines on economic viability, as well as standards (non-governmental) at national/international level and National Grant Program Guidelines. However, 3 respondents mentioned they do not use or do not know the guidelines/standards for economic viability. It was felt that existing guidelines/standards can be helpful to obtain a general preview of the economic balance, get clear cost structure, enable comparisons, include full building life cycle and provide a basis for long-term decision making. Two categories of challenges were identified - either related to historic buildings/conservation works (difficulty in estimating conservation works and complexity of calculations for heritage buildings) or issues about the difficulty to estimate/anticipate construction costs in general (market price volatility, uncertainty of long-term economic forecasts and the fact that guidelines/standards do not reflect the current status of the construction market).

The tools mentioned by respondents to perform this step could be split between three categories: dedicated commercial software programs, using an in-house tool (e.g. custom LCC Excel formulas) or analysing basic data on running costs. There are various cost management software programs, and these may have variations - they can or cannot be integrated with BIM and can or cannot include LCC calculations. One respondent made the general comment that he is not using LCC because there is too much uncertainty about future costs and construction materials or products lifespan. It was also mentioned, as an issue, that a software program was not officially required by any institution at the national level.

There were various divergences in the feedback received as to when this step should take place – during the stage when a light-touch design is being informed, at a more developed design stage and at the tender stage or at each stage when a cost is presented to the client.

Environmental impact (e.g. Life cycle assessment, waste) - (4 respondents)

There was no consensus among the respondents on the guidelines/standards to assess the environmental impact of retrofit projects. Guidelines/standards for environmental impact that were

mentioned by respondents were diverse and included construction legislation/standards at national level, energy performance of buildings legislation/standards at national level, environmental legislation at national level, environmental standards (non-governmental) at national level and internal procedures. One respondent mentioned he did not use any guidelines/standards. Feedback included advantages and inconveniences, although this was not requested in the practitioner form used. Existing guidelines/standards can be helpful to grow environmental awareness but there is a high cost associated when conducting these analyses, and a lack of specific guidelines for heritage buildings.

The feedback on tools mentioned by respondents to perform this step was diverse due to the diversity of environmental impact aspects tools could help with. Different tools/approaches were mentioned: software programs for environmental impact, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) software programs, and carbon footprint calculators (either inhouse or commercial tools) sometimes primarily focused on operational energy rather than embodied carbon. One respondent said they do not do pre-demolition audits whilst another respondent said they do not use these tools. It was highlighted that tools were available. However, one respondent said that there is a lack of reliable databases of materials and products, and that this is a big issue with LCA evaluations. One respondent said they are currently upskilling in whole life carbon assessment (being more focused on the cradle to gate, i.e. the A modules of whole life assessment, and on operational energy).

There was clear feedback that this step should take place at a more developed design stage or building permit stage.

2.2.2. Overall analysis across all “steps” and proposals to address identified issues

The table below summarises the key findings from the respondents’ feedback for each of the “steps,” i.e. the most important technical/practical aspects or considerations associated with the energy retrofit of historic buildings.

Step	Guideline/standard	Tool (software, ...)	When
Heritage value assessment	<p>Clear guidelines and standards at a high level.</p> <p><i>Proposal: Develop guidelines/standards to help adapt the high-level heritage value assessment process to individual buildings (facilitating and mainstreaming the process)</i></p>	<p>No tool mentioned, rather tasks to be performed.</p> <p><i>Proposal: Create simple tool for heritage significance analysis (facilitating and mainstreaming the process)</i></p>	At the beginning of the retrofit process.
Assessment of the use of the building	<p>Clear guidelines and standards for structural requirements but not enough for assessing use and space planning.</p> <p><i>Proposal: Develop high-level guidelines/standards for assessing use and space planning in historic</i></p>	<p>Some tools mentioned as well as tasks to be performed.</p> <p><i>Proposal: Create a tool for understanding users’ use of the building and requirements</i></p>	At the beginning of the retrofit process.

	<i>buildings</i>		
Condition survey and technical documentation	<p>Guidelines and standards available.</p> <p><i>Proposal: To be developed further</i></p>	<p>Some tools mentioned.</p> <p><i>Proposal: Create a tool for building pathology survey and for surveying structural capacity of internal structures</i></p>	<p>Beginning of the retrofit process.</p> <p>Could also happen at a later point in the project too - during the building permit stage.</p>
Energy performance assessment	<p>Many overlapping and sometimes contradictory guidelines and standards.</p> <p><i>Proposal: Create a unified document (at a high level) to provide a clear process and to signpost to relevant guidelines/standards?</i></p>	<p>A lot of tools are available - either integrated or very specific. Sometimes very complex and time consuming.</p> <p><i>Proposal: Can these tools be optimised for easier use and efficiency? Can some of them be more high-level to support a solution appraisal exercise (comparing possible technical solutions) at an early stage in the project and in a holistic way?</i></p>	<p>During developed design stage or building permit stage. Potentially at several design stages.</p>
Indoor environmental assessment	<p>A lot of guidelines and standards but this leads to some contradictions, and they are intrinsically complex.</p> <p><i>Proposal: Create a unified document (at a high level) to provide a clear process and to signpost to relevant guidelines/standards?</i></p>	<p>Some tools mentioned as well as tasks to be performed.</p> <p><i>Proposal: Create a tool for post occupancy evaluation and interviewing users?</i></p>	<p>No clear consensus – could potentially happen at any time in the project depending on objectives.</p>

Economic viability	Few guidelines and standards (and/or no knowledge of them, not in use). <i>Proposal: Develop guidance on a process to assess economic viability and specifically on the use of LCC for historic buildings?</i>	Tools available. <i>Proposal: Develop additional tools at two levels – easy to use (e.g. running cost analysis) or at a more detailed (e.g. LCC)?</i>	No clear consensus – could potentially happen at any time in the project depending on objectives.
Environmental impact	Guidelines and standards are diverse – not clear “go-to” documents. <i>Proposal: Develop guidelines covering all aspects of environmental impact for historic buildings?</i>	Tools available but are numerous and sometimes very specialised. <i>Proposal: Develop simple tools on LCA based on reliable databases and on waste?</i>	At a more developed design stage or building permit stage.

Table 5. Overall analysis across all “steps” of the respondents to the practitioner form

2.3. Interpretation of results

2.3.1. Survey and Interviews

Taking all responses into account, there are several conclusions and potential next steps to be undertaken.

Improvements in public opinion or awareness raising, better understanding of the inherent energy efficiency of historic buildings, and increased training and skills development for traditional craftsmanship were all suggested or referenced by respondents and would certainly be welcome advances and improve the efforts to retrofit historic buildings, but of primary concern for most respondents is the need to improve policy and legislation. Historic buildings are placed at a disadvantage wherever energy efficiency building policy is created primarily with new construction in mind. Respondents were not in agreement whether existing legislation and policy should be adjusted to better reflect the needs of historic buildings or entirely separate policies should be put in place specifically for historic buildings, and this is a question that will no doubt require further study. It is also important to recognize that these concerns are interlinked, and a holistic approach taking all of these concerns into consideration is most likely to succeed going forward.

Sorrell et al (2000) divided barriers into three different overarching categories: economic, behavioural and organizational, while emphasizing that the main barriers to energy efficiency can vary significantly depending on the sector or organization, and that it is unlikely that a single policy approach will work universally across sectors. Instead, they argue that a diverse range of strategies will be needed, designed to address the distinct characteristics of each situation. As a result, effective policy solutions should be tailored to the circumstances of each energy-using sector, based on an analysis of barriers for that sector.

Energy retrofits in historic buildings is fundamentally different from standard energy retrofits as it is

posited in the intersection of two different policy objectives: 1) improving buildings from a technical point of view to make them more resource efficient, improve the indoor climate, reduce emissions etc, and 2) preserve the heritage significance of individual buildings and heritage values in the built environment at large. This specific position calls for a customized analysis of barriers across the multiple stakeholder groups involved in retrofit. It also makes the barrier analysis more complex, as the barriers could be defined in relation to the two different policy objectives. In essence, is the identified barrier a barrier to improved energy efficiency or a barrier to improved heritage preservation (or both)?

2.3.2. Practitioner Forms

Whilst the respondent sample used to collect data was small with six respondents covering the four demonstration site countries, some general trends could still be drawn from the data analysis.

For instance, there was clarity amongst respondents regarding the guidelines and standards practitioners should use for heritage value assessment and energy performance assessment, and those guidelines and standards are national and international. The feedback collected indicated these guidelines and standards need to be refined to address some issues such as their applicability to individual buildings for heritage value assessment and their complexity for energy performance assessment. However, the feedback collected for tools led to the conclusion that different approaches are needed: new tools are required to support the heritage value assessment process whilst existing tools for energy performance assessment need simplifying and optimising. It is clear that simpler/more guidance is needed for indoor environmental assessment, economic viability and environmental impact, and tools may need to be created or simplified to become easier to use.

In some cases, there is no clear trend that emerges from the results. This is the case for the guidelines and standards related to environmental impact; there is no “go-to” document that compiles all the required information. As a result, respondents mentioned a large number of distinctive documents. Similarly, it is not clear in respondents’ feedback when indoor environmental assessment activities should be performed – guidelines could be created to address this gap.

Frequently, respondents mentioned tasks to be performed as part of the retrofit process but not tools required to perform them. Tools may not always be necessary, but this should prompt some reflection as to whether there is a gap to be addressed – e.g. for the heritage value assessment “step”, the tasks mentioned by respondents included studying the history of the building and its context, carrying out a site visit and analysing the significance of the building. This phenomenon was quite recurrent for the “steps” heritage value assessment, assessment of the use of the building, condition survey and technical documentation. An explanation could be that the work related to these tasks is mostly performed by practitioners through her/his analysis of the data that is collected and own skills/knowledge, rather than the use of dedicated tools.

Sometimes respondents mentioned that they did not use or are not aware of any guidelines/standards and tools for specific “steps” of the retrofit project. There can be several explanations for this.

One is the size of the architectural practice and their specialisation (heritage, energy retrofit, public/commercial or residential buildings, etc.). Bigger practices will tend to use more complex tools (either commercial tools or developing in-house tools) whilst smaller practices may not use specific tools or would develop simple in-house tools. Specialised practices in energy retrofit will use more tools in that area than practices specialised in heritage – the latter could instead subcontract energy retrofit specialists on specific projects if required. As a consequence, if practitioners do not know the tools for a specific task to be performed, this does not mean there are no tools available. It is also important to mention that given the small size of the sample, some conclusions may need further

confirmation from additional practitioners. For instance, respondents are not mentioning specific tools relating to structural surveys of historic buildings because this is not their area of expertise, if there are architects; this does not mean there are no tools available. As such, a careful analysis of the trends should be performed to avoid a misinterpretation of the data collected.

Therefore, the approach and the toolkit developed in Work Package 4 and other related Work Packages should take into account the targeted audience in their full diversity, when it comes to practitioners (e.g. small and size architectural practices, their specialisation), and should seek to fully understand and address their requirements – for the retrofit approach and toolkit to be widely used.

Another explanation in terms of different habits when using tools could be linked to national legislations or mandatory standards that may impose the use of specific tools. Overall and whilst there are many commonalities between each country in the respondents' feedback, it is important to keep in mind that some aspects of the process of retrofitting historic buildings are influenced by the local context, i.e. where the project is being implemented, prompting the use of specific tools or guidelines.

As such, the approach and the toolkit developed in Work Package 4 and other related work packages should take into account, to some extent (i.e. at a high level), the local context of the countries in which the tools will be applied – or at least include caveats/checklists for users so they can adapt this toolkit/approach to their own local context/requirements.

3. Conclusions and Outlook

The FuturHist Barrier Survey, together with the interviews, provided detailed information on the identification of barriers to the energy retrofitting of historic buildings, while data collected amongst practitioners from the four demonstration site countries using “practitioner forms” highlighted general trends observable across the continent on the guidelines/standards and tools used by practitioners for each of the main “steps” of any retrofit project.

Principle findings from the survey show that barriers of a regulatory nature are the most significant faced by stakeholders, with 30% of respondents citing individual barriers in that category, followed by references to financial barriers made by 24% of respondents. Yet the fact that barriers identified by respondents fell across all six barrier categories (regulatory, financial, awareness and mindset, technical, knowledge and skills gap, and planning related) without any one overwhelming majority shows the interconnected nature of these barriers.

The structured interviews gave more detailed insight into how these barriers and barrier categories are often intertwined. Interviewees gave concrete examples from their own experiences to illustrate this. The Scottish architect working as a retrofit designer (PRAUK1) gave the example of how conservation restrictions prevent installing external insulation of a facade (regulatory barrier), with internal insulation mentioned as a viable alternative. However, this option reduces the overall available living space (technical barriers) and impacts on the property value (financial barrier) and technical pitfalls have to be considered (technical barriers).

Analysing the practitioner forms, key findings show that while there is clarity on guidelines and standards that practitioners use for some of the 7 identified “steps” of the retrofit process, others are notably lacking, along with tools. In some instances, there are multiple tools being used by practitioners and no clear consensus on “go-to” guidelines/standards. Practitioners frequently mentioned necessary tasks to be performed, but less frequently the tools required to do so. However, this does not necessarily mean that there are no tools existing; in some cases, it may instead mean that no tools are required for certain activities. It is also important to mention that given the small size of the sample of practitioners and their profiles, some conclusions need to be dealt with carefully and further confirmation from additional practitioners may be required.

Furthermore, there is a correlation between the key findings from the survey, interviews and practitioner forms, especially in references to regulatory and financial barriers. Respondents to all activities expressed concerns in some way regarding the costs associated with the energy retrofitting of historic buildings and the costs of necessary tools for practitioners. Along with the Scottish architect (PRAUK1), other respondents like the deputy head of a real estate company in Poland (PROPL2), pointed to the lack of cost-effective solutions specifically acceptable to conservation authorities.

It is also important to acknowledge the influence of local contexts to any barrier identified in these activities. Identical barriers referenced by stakeholders operating in different local contexts are not necessarily addressed and resolved in identical ways. One example is the Spanish heritage expert working for a public authority (PUBES1) who witnessed caution in working on projects with European funding, something that was not referenced by respondents from northern Europe. Local contexts of culture, climate, and laws and regulations must be accounted for going forward. If properly understood, local contexts can offer as much hindrance as assistance to the process of addressing identified barriers. Local knowledge especially can be a significant form of assistance; adapting

strategies to local necessities. However, local knowledge is often built up and developed over time, and it can be difficult to challenge deeply held notions when they prove to be counterproductive to the retrofit process. This is especially the case within the professional-client relationship.

The lack of direct input from private owners of historic buildings is a major challenge. It remains difficult to effectively communicate en-masse with private owners in the same way as with professional practitioners or representatives of public authorities and, as such, the stakeholder group remains somewhat underrepresented in the feedback collected.

Moving forward, the key findings from this work package should considerably help in the proper understanding of the target audience for the approach and toolkit developed in Work Package 4 (“Development of an integrated planning toolkit”), and Work Package 6 (“Scale-up”). Practitioners will be specifically targeted for the toolkit and methodologies, with the key findings from this work package directly assisting these developments. The survey, interviews, and practitioner forms will provide a better understanding of the diversity of practitioners, their local contexts, and their specific requirements. This data will also support the creation of specific policy proposals to address some of these barriers in Work Package 6 and its Task 6.2, which will be then disseminated amongst heritage authorities from European countries.

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5. Annexes

Annex 1 - WP1 FuturHist Barrier Survey – Original Survey Form

FuturHist Barrier Survey

FuturHist aims to develop replicable retrofit solutions for historic buildings of the future. See more about the project at <https://futurhist.eu/>

The aim of this survey is to identify barriers to energy retrofit of historic buildings. The term "historic buildings" is here used to include all buildings with heritage values, both listed and non-listed.

The survey is short and should take around 10 minutes to fill in.

If you have any questions about the survey, please contact us.

Data management/consent

The personal data you provide to ICOMOS/ FuturHist with this survey will be treated in accordance with the ICOMOS' Privacy Policy, and in compliance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). ICOMOS does not store personal data longer than it is reasonably useful or required by law. By sharing all other data in this survey, you consent that ICOMOS and the consortium partners within the FuturHist project may use them for analytical and research purposes, and publish them as part of the project deliverables.

* Spørgsmålet er obligatorisk

FuturHist

1. Name

2. In which country are you based? *

3. What is your profession? *

4. Are you a member of FuturHist? *

Markér alle, du er enig i.

Yes

No

5. Are you a member of ICOMOS? *

Markér kun ét felt.

Yes, I'm a member of Icomos

No, I'm not a member of Icomos

6. If you are a member of Icomos, please let us know which National committee or International scientific committee

7. Which e-mail address shall we use to contact you?

Barriers

8. What do you think are the main barriers to making historic buildings more energy efficient?

9. The expertise/skill among professionals involved in energy retrofits of historic buildings is sufficient

Markér kun ét felt.

1 2 3 4 5

No, | Absolutely!

10. Please specify what kind of expertise/skills that are lacking (if you think that is the case)

11. Are there generally enough good examples of energy retrofit in historic buildings? *

Markér kun ét felt.

1 2 3 4 5

No, | Absolutely!

12. What kind of good examples would you like to have more of?

13. Do policies regarding renovation of historic buildings support the planning of energy retrofit in an effective way? With policies we refer to national, regional and local planning policies.

Markér kun ét felt.

1 2 3 4 5

No, I Absolutely

14. If you can, please give examples of how policies can be a barrier in the planning process

15. Is there sufficient publicly available support and guidance for the energy retrofit of historic buildings?

Markér kun ét felt.

1 2 3 4 5

No, I Absolutely

16. What kind of support/guidance is missing?

17. Are you aware of a best practice database for energy retrofit of historic buildings? If so, please share any link or sources.

18. Is it possible to get public funding for the energy retrofit of listed buildings? If yes, for what kind of measures?

19. Is it possible to get public funding for the energy retrofit of non-listed buildings? If yes, for what kind of measures?

20. Is there funding for maintenance (accompanying measures or follow-up costs beyond the main measure)

21. Is there funding to subsidise the repair of existing buildings, or is only a new measure considered eligible for funding?

22. Is there anything more that you would like to add regarding barriers to energy retrofit in historic buildings?

Step 2 - structured interview

In a second phase we would like to do follow-up interviews. The interviews will be made online and don't require any preparation.

23. Can we contact you for a follow-up interview? *

Markér kun ét felt.

Yes

No

24. Are there other individuals that you think that we should contact for an interview? Please also provide contact information if you have.

Dette indhold er hverken oprettet eller godkendt af Google.

Google Analyse

Annex 2 - WP1 Survey – Anonymised Raw Survey Data

Country	In which country are you based?	Region	Stakeholder group	What is your profession?	Professional Sector	Are you a member of ICCROM?	Are you a member of ICCROM?	Are you a member of ICCROM?	What is your role in the building energy retrofit process?	The knowledge and skills you possess in the building energy retrofit process?	What are the main barriers to energy retrofits in historic buildings?	Are there any specific energy retrofit measures that you consider to be particularly important for historic buildings?	What kind of energy retrofit measures do you think are most important for historic buildings?	What kind of energy retrofit measures do you think are most important for historic buildings?	What kind of energy retrofit measures do you think are most important for historic buildings?	Are you aware of a best practice database for energy retrofit of historic buildings? If so, please share any links or sources.	Is it possible to get public funding for the energy retrofit of historic buildings? If so, please share any links or sources.	Is there funding for maintenance (conservation) measures of historic buildings beyond the main measures?	Is there funding to subsidize the repair of existing buildings, or is only a few measures and repairing them to energy retrofit considered eligible for funding?	Is there anything more that you would like to mention in relation to energy retrofit of historic buildings?
1	Spain	Southern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	Yes	No, I'm not a member of ICCROM	N/A	Urban regeneration, lack of knowledge, cost of intervention vs. benefits	Urban regeneration, lack of knowledge, cost of intervention vs. benefits	Urban regeneration, lack of knowledge, cost of intervention vs. benefits	Urban regeneration, lack of knowledge, cost of intervention vs. benefits	Urban regeneration, lack of knowledge, cost of intervention vs. benefits	Urban regeneration, lack of knowledge, cost of intervention vs. benefits	Urban regeneration, lack of knowledge, cost of intervention vs. benefits	Yes, in Netherlands https://www.domeproject.nl ; in France: https://www.observeatour.com/batimentspatrimoine	Yes, but they are not considered energy saving	Yes, there are many funding programs, usually they require and improvement of the building energy efficiency. In Italy, Superbonus with related measures (soon to be replaced)	Yes, it exists, and there are different programs at national and regional level (but changes greatly from region to region)	Need to mention the risk of gentrification of a social gap and a situation of social inequality due to the unequal market conditions of the same of housing...
2	Italy	Southern Europe	academia	Researcher	Academia and Research	Yes	Yes, I'm a member of ICCROM	ISCES	Cost of intervention vs. benefits	Cost of intervention vs. benefits	Cost of intervention vs. benefits	Cost of intervention vs. benefits	Cost of intervention vs. benefits	Cost of intervention vs. benefits	Cost of intervention vs. benefits	Yes, in Netherlands https://www.domeproject.nl ; in France: https://www.observeatour.com/batimentspatrimoine	Yes, but they are not considered energy saving	Yes, there are many funding programs, usually they require and improvement of the building energy efficiency. In Italy, Superbonus with related measures (soon to be replaced)	Yes, it exists, and there are different programs at national and regional level (but changes greatly from region to region)	Need to mention the risk of gentrification of a social gap and a situation of social inequality due to the unequal market conditions of the same of housing...
3	North Macedonia	Southern Europe	academia	Researcher	Academia and Research	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICCROM	North Macedonia	Gap in the knowledge needed for making historic buildings more energy efficient. Also, lack of the staff with the finance and money needed	Expertise in sustainable materials and energy efficiency for historic buildings. Also, lack of the staff with the finance and money needed	Expertise in sustainable materials and energy efficiency for historic buildings. Also, lack of the staff with the finance and money needed	Expertise in sustainable materials and energy efficiency for historic buildings. Also, lack of the staff with the finance and money needed	Expertise in sustainable materials and energy efficiency for historic buildings. Also, lack of the staff with the finance and money needed	Expertise in sustainable materials and energy efficiency for historic buildings. Also, lack of the staff with the finance and money needed	Expertise in sustainable materials and energy efficiency for historic buildings. Also, lack of the staff with the finance and money needed	Yes, in Netherlands https://www.domeproject.nl ; in France: https://www.observeatour.com/batimentspatrimoine	Yes, but they are not considered energy saving	Yes, there are many funding programs, usually they require and improvement of the building energy efficiency. In Italy, Superbonus with related measures (soon to be replaced)	Yes, it exists, and there are different programs at national and regional level (but changes greatly from region to region)	Need to mention the risk of gentrification of a social gap and a situation of social inequality due to the unequal market conditions of the same of housing...
4	Denmark	Northern Europe	practitioners	Professor, Architect	Academia and Research	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICCROM	Denmark	The building energy retrofit is not supported through the legislation	Knowledge on all levels from architecture and the building industry	Knowledge on all levels from architecture and the building industry	Knowledge on all levels from architecture and the building industry	Knowledge on all levels from architecture and the building industry	Knowledge on all levels from architecture and the building industry	Knowledge on all levels from architecture and the building industry	Yes, in Netherlands https://www.domeproject.nl ; in France: https://www.observeatour.com/batimentspatrimoine	Yes, but they are not considered energy saving	Yes, there are many funding programs, usually they require and improvement of the building energy efficiency. In Italy, Superbonus with related measures (soon to be replaced)	Yes, it exists, and there are different programs at national and regional level (but changes greatly from region to region)	Need to mention the risk of gentrification of a social gap and a situation of social inequality due to the unequal market conditions of the same of housing...
5	Sweden	Northern Europe	academia	Researcher	Academia and Research	Yes	Yes, I'm a member of ICCROM	Sweden	Lack of knowledge about the value of historic buildings, both as resources and as heritage. Lack of knowledge about the value of historic buildings, both as resources and as heritage. Lack of knowledge about the value of historic buildings, both as resources and as heritage.	During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process. During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process. During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process.	During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process. During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process. During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process.	During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process. During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process. During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process.	During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process. During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process. During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process.	During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process. During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process. During the planning stage, there are different stages in the process.	Yes, in Netherlands https://www.domeproject.nl ; in France: https://www.observeatour.com/batimentspatrimoine	Yes, but they are not considered energy saving	Yes, there are many funding programs, usually they require and improvement of the building energy efficiency. In Italy, Superbonus with related measures (soon to be replaced)	Yes, it exists, and there are different programs at national and regional level (but changes greatly from region to region)	Need to mention the risk of gentrification of a social gap and a situation of social inequality due to the unequal market conditions of the same of housing...	
6	UK	Northern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICCROM	NC - ICCROM, Historic England, ICC, ISCES, ICOMOS and ICFP	(1) Inadequate and capacity for energy retrofit. (2) Inadequate financial capacity	Energy assessment and digital documentation of historic buildings	Energy assessment and digital documentation of historic buildings	Energy assessment and digital documentation of historic buildings	Energy assessment and digital documentation of historic buildings	Energy assessment and digital documentation of historic buildings	Yes, in Netherlands https://www.domeproject.nl ; in France: https://www.observeatour.com/batimentspatrimoine	Yes, but they are not considered energy saving	Yes, there are many funding programs, usually they require and improvement of the building energy efficiency. In Italy, Superbonus with related measures (soon to be replaced)	Yes, it exists, and there are different programs at national and regional level (but changes greatly from region to region)	Need to mention the risk of gentrification of a social gap and a situation of social inequality due to the unequal market conditions of the same of housing...	
7	Austria	Central Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICCROM	Austria	Besides inefficiency, power usage is a big problem. Besides inefficiency, power usage is a big problem. Besides inefficiency, power usage is a big problem.	Examples that are not fancy and expensive, but would be a major concern	Examples that are not fancy and expensive, but would be a major concern	Examples that are not fancy and expensive, but would be a major concern	Examples that are not fancy and expensive, but would be a major concern	Examples that are not fancy and expensive, but would be a major concern	Yes, in Netherlands https://www.domeproject.nl ; in France: https://www.observeatour.com/batimentspatrimoine	Yes, but they are not considered energy saving	Yes, there are many funding programs, usually they require and improvement of the building energy efficiency. In Italy, Superbonus with related measures (soon to be replaced)	Yes, it exists, and there are different programs at national and regional level (but changes greatly from region to region)	Need to mention the risk of gentrification of a social gap and a situation of social inequality due to the unequal market conditions of the same of housing...	
8	Estonia	Northern Europe	practitioners	Engineer-Consultant	Engineering and Construction	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICCROM	Estonia	Lack of historical guidelines that include specific technical details and local building details and materials. Lack of historical guidelines that include specific technical details and local building details and materials.	Architectural detailing and construction of historic buildings	Yes, in Netherlands https://www.domeproject.nl ; in France: https://www.observeatour.com/batimentspatrimoine	Yes, but they are not considered energy saving	Yes, there are many funding programs, usually they require and improvement of the building energy efficiency. In Italy, Superbonus with related measures (soon to be replaced)	Yes, it exists, and there are different programs at national and regional level (but changes greatly from region to region)	Need to mention the risk of gentrification of a social gap and a situation of social inequality due to the unequal market conditions of the same of housing...					

9	Belgium	Central Europe	public authority	advisor research programme at the government agency responsible for cultural heritage	Cultural Heritage Professionals	No	Yes, I'm a member of ISCES	regulations that are to strict and slow methods to secure the energy of historic buildings	restoration architects and environment lack expertise and materials 2. but not enough to restore the facade is to insulate and not on installations	low carbon 2. restorations in buildings	politics mostly prevent one side or the other 3. do not respect the building 4. do not respect the building	guidance by professionals that is up to date and mostly given by the building	yes, members of protected heritage use EPC label (EPC) label a fine labelled heritage energy advice all owners of protected buildings use get a permit to work on a heritage project, you can get a heritage grant (with a maximum of 250,000 euros) for the conservation of buildings with heritage value	yes, the heritage team up to 250,000 € is also for non listed buildings, mentioned in the inventory of buildings with heritage value	Yes. For periodic maintenance work and small projects, you can get a heritage grant (with a maximum of 250,000 euros) for the conservation of buildings with heritage value	Yes there is a grant for existing buildings (according to selected theme and via call) and there is a heritage loan	no						
10	Ireland	Northern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of ISCES	Access to appropriate skills/ financial and human resources - both for the planning and design stages as well as the implementation work. insufficient data on actual performance of historic buildings, poor project leads, programmes and funding opportunities. The applicant understands what is involved in restoring historic buildings most energy efficient (often relevant for larger public and commercial projects, and commercial and residential construction.	There is need for both additional skills/ professionals with current knowledge in conservation and more technical knowledge as well as greater access to testing and costed information. 2. difficult to access the right skills, what is required is not always available. 3. historic buildings are not always seen as a legal and technical challenge, as well as the heritage value, and understanding the technical performance of	a good diversity of building typologies and contexts. This crucial socio modest interventions as well as the design. One building type often a lot more complex than a residential occupancy. 2. historic buildings are not always seen as a legal and technical challenge, as well as the heritage value, and understanding the technical performance of	In Ireland the policy landscape is complex and confusing for many. There is national policy and legislation, but the planning process is complex and confusing. The Energy Efficiency in Historic Buildings (EHB) Act 2014 provides a framework for the Energy Efficiency in Historic Buildings (EHB) Act 2014. The EHB Act 2014 provides a framework for the Energy Efficiency in Historic Buildings (EHB) Act 2014. The EHB Act 2014 provides a framework for the Energy Efficiency in Historic Buildings (EHB) Act 2014.	To start with some of what is available, or not available - recently published national guidance in Energy Efficiency in Historic Buildings (EHB) Act 2014. The EHB Act 2014 provides a framework for the Energy Efficiency in Historic Buildings (EHB) Act 2014. The EHB Act 2014 provides a framework for the Energy Efficiency in Historic Buildings (EHB) Act 2014.	There is no funding specifically for listed buildings, however there is a general funding scheme available which is also open to listed buildings. See answer above if not for funding of historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general.	There is no funding specifically for listed buildings, however there is a general funding scheme available which is also open to listed buildings. See answer above if not for funding of historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general.	There is no funding specifically for listed buildings, however there is a general funding scheme available which is also open to listed buildings. See answer above if not for funding of historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general.	There is no funding specifically for listed buildings, however there is a general funding scheme available which is also open to listed buildings. See answer above if not for funding of historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general.	There is no funding specifically for listed buildings, however there is a general funding scheme available which is also open to listed buildings. See answer above if not for funding of historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general.	There is no funding specifically for listed buildings, however there is a general funding scheme available which is also open to listed buildings. See answer above if not for funding of historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general.	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There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general.	There is no funding specifically for listed buildings, however there is a general funding scheme available which is also open to listed buildings. See answer above if not for funding of historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general.	There is no funding specifically for listed buildings, however there is a general funding scheme available which is also open to listed buildings. See answer above if not for funding of historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general. There is a grant for historic buildings in general.
11	North Macedonia	Southern Europe	practitioners	civil engineer, specialist in earthquake engineering	Engineering and Construction	No	Yes, I'm a member of ISCES	the cost of the medium and that application in the case of building with no need for facade	skills for proper application of energy retrofit	Integrated seismic and energy retrofitting	when they do not provide financial support	first, for doing the assessment, and then for the no other possibilities	listed buildings in country with preserved facade, or facade interventions is possible	There is no such possibility, unless it is granted from other financial instruments out of our country	only for listed buildings, but based on the project prepared for as a new measure	In North Macedonia the imperative is to develop data base with essential information that is used for the assessment and introducing the owners with the possible solution							
12	Azerbaijan	Southern Europe	practitioners	Cultural heritage specialist	Cultural Heritage Professionals	No	Yes, I'm a member of ISCES	I think in the case of the country the lack of professional historic building energy efficient is the main gap. The main gap is the lack of professional historic building energy efficient is the main gap. The main gap is the lack of professional historic building energy efficient is the main gap.	Experts in sustainability and energy consumption	Integrated seismic and energy retrofitting	when they do not provide financial support	first, for doing the assessment, and then for the no other possibilities	listed buildings in country with preserved facade, or facade interventions is possible	There is no such possibility, unless it is granted from other financial instruments out of our country	only for listed buildings, but based on the project prepared for as a new measure	In North Macedonia the imperative is to develop data base with essential information that is used for the assessment and introducing the owners with the possible solution							
13	Portugal	Southern Europe	practitioners	Architect / Researcher	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of ISCES	Lack of contemporary research and transmission about the real performance	Understanding that the Energy Performance Certification are mostly a question for concrete buildings and that historic buildings had specific strategies	Neighborhood 3. building approaches	when they do not provide financial support	first, for doing the assessment, and then for the no other possibilities	listed buildings in country with preserved facade, or facade interventions is possible	There is no such possibility, unless it is granted from other financial instruments out of our country	only for listed buildings, but based on the project prepared for as a new measure	In North Macedonia the imperative is to develop data base with essential information that is used for the assessment and introducing the owners with the possible solution							
14	Turkey	Southern Europe	practitioners	Dr architect	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of ISCES	Extra comfort for the people and expertise and awareness	Awareness and energy knowledge	Neighborhood 3. building approaches	when they do not provide financial support	first, for doing the assessment, and then for the no other possibilities	listed buildings in country with preserved facade, or facade interventions is possible	There is no such possibility, unless it is granted from other financial instruments out of our country	only for listed buildings, but based on the project prepared for as a new measure	In North Macedonia the imperative is to develop data base with essential information that is used for the assessment and introducing the owners with the possible solution							
15	Norway	Northern Europe	academia	Professor of social science and lecturer of history	Academia and Research	No	Yes, I'm a member of ISCES	Under water cultural heritage	Understanding that the Energy Performance Certification are mostly a question for concrete buildings and that historic buildings had specific strategies	Neighborhood 3. building approaches	when they do not provide financial support	first, for doing the assessment, and then for the no other possibilities	listed buildings in country with preserved facade, or facade interventions is possible	There is no such possibility, unless it is granted from other financial instruments out of our country	only for listed buildings, but based on the project prepared for as a new measure	In North Macedonia the imperative is to develop data base with essential information that is used for the assessment and introducing the owners with the possible solution							
16	Turkey	Southern Europe	academia	Academic Staff	Academia and Research	No	Yes, I'm a member of ISCES	Legislation and awareness	Understanding that the Energy Performance Certification are mostly a question for concrete buildings and that historic buildings had specific strategies	Neighborhood 3. building approaches	when they do not provide financial support	first, for doing the assessment, and then for the no other possibilities	listed buildings in country with preserved facade, or facade interventions is possible	There is no such possibility, unless it is granted from other financial instruments out of our country	only for listed buildings, but based on the project prepared for as a new measure	In North Macedonia the imperative is to develop data base with essential information that is used for the assessment and introducing the owners with the possible solution							
17	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Southern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of ISCES	Impossible to work with materials and technologies	Contemporary 2. materials, technologies	Economic and 4. sustainable	when they do not provide financial support	first, for doing the assessment, and then for the no other possibilities	listed buildings in country with preserved facade, or facade interventions is possible	There is no such possibility, unless it is granted from other financial instruments out of our country	only for listed buildings, but based on the project prepared for as a new measure	In North Macedonia the imperative is to develop data base with essential information that is used for the assessment and introducing the owners with the possible solution							

35	Italy	Southern Europe	academia	University Professor	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of homes	The difficulty in integrating energy efficient solutions and HVAC systems	Being aware that the various solutions used in non-historic buildings are not as effective in historic buildings, thus different approaches must be considered.	Interesting examples of 3 conventional HVAC integration	Police commonly think on thermal 4 buildings, which is not always accurate in historic buildings.	2	Just IEA Task 59 "Renovating Historic Buildings Towards Zero Energy"	Yes, fiscal incentives are available for any energy retrofit measure. Yes, fiscal incentives are available for any energy performance measure. However, they are the same as for non-historic buildings.	Not aware of	Not aware of		
36	Italy	Southern Europe	academia	Researcher	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of homes	Need of protection	constructive and technical solutions. 2 renewable energy, seismic solutions, climate proof	climate adaptation and seismic 1 solutions, renewable energy integration	not considering the degree of a historic building protection	guidelines and rules for national and local architecture of 1 the local, state and federal levels, together with historical awareness and examples	HBE/HBAtlas, BIPV meets history, TABULA WebTool, Episcopi: HBAtlas	Grants are typically awarded for the insulation projects or retrofits that improve historical buildings energy efficiency. EU funds, instead of energy efficiency framing.	Grants are typically awarded for thermal insulation projects or retrofits for energy integration. Funds: The European Union (EU), the European Fund for Structural Investments (EFSD), Horizon 2020, and the EUREM facility specific programs in addition. There is a new LIFE	https://chitect.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Updating-the-Renovation-of-Historic-Buildings-in-Belgium-Final-deliverable-v2.pdf	European Commission's Renovation Wave Strategy	Inadequate management, oversight and assessment are among the obstacles facing historic conservation; absence of standard systems, cutting-edge technology, and insufficient preservation knowledge to maintain effective preservation
37	Italy	Southern Europe	practitioners	Construction Engineer	Engineering and Construction	No	No, I'm not a member of homes	First of all, Historical and Architectural Constraints protection of buildings, use of original materials (which are often not the most efficient), high costs (structural interventions and limited funding and regulations, long and lengthy administrative procedures.	Improving training, encouraging and promoting multidisciplinary collaboration and ensuring steps to ensure that skills meet the challenges.	Technological innovation, but also the possibility of 3 greater use of renewable resources (less exploitation of resources)	Administrative 2 procedures too long	2	A major hurdle in finding a balance between the need to preserve the historical and cultural integrity of buildings and energy efficiency. Not all owners of historic buildings are willing to invest in the available opportunities for energy efficiency. Even with incentives and funding, the energy retrofitting costs of historic buildings can be high, and not all owners can afford such investments.	For historic buildings, it is possible to obtain public funding for the energy retrofitting of buildings not only for economic, technical, or cultural reasons, but also for historical and local incentives granted by the Regional and Local governments. The main incentives are focused on energy upgrading (cold above) but there are opportunities to cover also maintenance and follow-up costs, provided that they are documented and relevant for the management of interventions	previous answer	no		
38	Belgium	Central Europe	academia	PhD student	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of homes	Strict Limitations on BEC installations, historical insulation materials, limited access to financial resources, the difficulty of upgrading due to complex layouts	Energy efficiency constraints for historic buildings, construction professionals with experience in historic buildings, legal and regulatory advice	3	Comprehensive and integrated approach that combine energy efficiency with preservation requirements, training and education, coordination between stakeholders	2	Comprehensive and integrated approach that combine energy efficiency with preservation requirements, training and education, coordination between stakeholders	Fiscal incentives	The same Fiscal incentives	Locally, but very rare	N.A.	
39	Italy	Southern Europe	practitioners	Civil Engineer	Engineering and Construction	No	No, I'm not a member of homes	Restrictions from the conservation authority	An integrated architectural-energetic approach	Substitution of intervention components 2 Energy Sources 3 Integration of Energy Sources	In many cases Renewable Energy 2 Sources are not allowed, nor is the source substitution	2	Clear and agreed (not available) regulation Eurat's Historic Building Energy Retrofit Atlas	Fiscal incentives	The same Fiscal incentives	Locally, but very rare	N.A.	
40	Italy	Southern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	No	No, I'm not a member of homes	Historic buildings are usually characterized by a value system that must be preserved. In the particular cases, an intervention system or interventions could challenge both the preservation of the appearance. In fact, there could be incompatibilities for the occurrence of rigid insulation or degradation phenomena, introducing ventilation modern plant systems sometimes does not	4	4 analysis and research, floor insulation against the ground, without compromising the existing floor	Sometimes in Italy, protection policy are so 4 compromising to prevent floor insulation stakeholders make informed decisions.	3	More detailed case studies showcasing successful retrofit projects, including the challenges faced and solutions implemented, would be valuable. (1) https://bea.be/en/academic/colloquium-be-uni-1.html (2) https://www.architecturalintelligence.com/en/energy-retrofit-historic-buildings/ page 2 (3) https://www.eurobarometer.eu/	There are some measures in Italy to encourage owners in retrofitting Superbonus 70% Deductions For: Thermal insulation Intervention. For vertical, horizontal or vertical opaque surfaces affecting more than 25% of the building's facade. Installation of Photovoltaic Solar Systems. Specific interventions. Installation of Changing Batteries for Electric Vehicles. Installation of Photovoltaic Systems. Commission of Architectural Barriers. Economic: the Superbonus (SPB) or BEC (deduction) recognized for energy rehabilitation works on single-family homes and condominiums. Depending on the intervention, incentives can vary from a maximum of 50% to a maximum of 70%. Specifically, a 50% rate is provided for the following interventions:	I don't know if there is something specific.	The question is not clear enough		
41	Austria	Central Europe	public authority	Consultant	Site/Project Management	No	No, I'm not a member of homes	Laws	4	3	2	2						

42	Italy	Southern Europe	academia	PhD Candidate	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of someone	Italy may be a lack awareness or expertise among building owners and contractors regarding how to effectively and sensitively improve energy efficiency in historic buildings. In case of failed buildings, solutions might be more expensive than the normal ones. Limited availability of funding specific for historic buildings energy retrofit.	3	4	2	The HBEIAtlas	I don't know	EcoBonus in Italy	As far as I know, there is no					
43	UK	Northern Europe	public authority, practitioners	Heritage conservation professional and digital development coordinator	Cultural Heritage Professionals	No	Yes, I'm a member of someone	United Kingdom	funding and support available	The problem is to identify the right and an for specific work. And we might not have enough resources with the health and skill sets.	A history of refurbishment projects would be useful to understand how refurbishment will look like in 40-50 years. There will be enough products to be replaced by them. This could help avoid maladaptations.	In the United Kingdom, even-odd construction is exempt from planning requirements. The energy efficiency of buildings you need to pay VAT.	financial support is available for the energy efficiency of buildings of cultural significance	https://heritagetrust.org.uk/whom-we-serve	Yes, but not specifically targeting for listed buildings and often not particularly suitable	No, public funding is not generally available for heritage	No, public funding is not generally available for repair	Good luck with the project FuturHist!		
44	Italy	Southern Europe	practitioners, academia	Industrial PhD student	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of someone		The (right) respect to historical/cultural value	In case of projects they are not aware of the historic background	Real good projects even if of urban buildings	In Italy we had 110 agencies, even without adequate energy efficiency values, running an entire building stock (other than)	Curious but not public	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344744444	no					
45	Germany	Central Europe	practitioners, academia	Architect, Researcher Building Sector	Architecture and Design	No	No, I'm not a member of someone		lack of energy interaction with historic buildings in general, lack of smart and sufficient solutions dealing with sufficient comfort levels	HVAC and electric systems integration is a sufficient and creative way	envelope technologies and other well-known solutions not at all	lack of knowledge of heritage authorities (who will describe the rules) concerning technical equipment and solutions	understandable described in various publications concerning technical equipment and good practices	no	change of windows, heating system, renewables	change of windows, heating system, renewables, envelope	no	funding only for cultural heritage important parts	low EU thresholds for EU wide tenders → high administration loads. No clear definition of quality of materials, the way to be required at the building, the importance on the heritage building and the definition of costs for the contractors. Same for monitoring of the results	
46	Germany	Central Europe	academia	Scientist	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of someone		Building practice (thermal envelope, durability elements worth preserving)	cross-sectional expertise about monument preservation, energy efficiency, design	2	2	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	New measures	Some owners hesitate to retrofit because of the high expenses and ignorance		
47	France	Central Europe	practitioners	Engineer	Engineering and Construction	No	No, I'm not a member of someone		Costs, knowledge of adapted solutions, even more actors than usual (heritage professionals, but advice from professionals)	Crisespeople with excellent skills to assist for they are not always called by contractors to work on historic buildings. Buildings owners have no idea of the heritage significance of their buildings, then they hire contractors that have no idea either. A contractor specialized in historic buildings will find the right challenge.	I would like to have a lot of examples, but not always perfect.	Practices do exist, but buildings owners sometimes are late in their project, but adding to their previous at the very end of the project makes it harder to do in the beginning	There is no specific public funding in the energy retrofit of listed buildings in France. For the energy retrofit, the only way for the restoration of listed buildings, yes.	There is no specific public funding in the energy retrofit of listed buildings in France. For the energy retrofit, the only way for the restoration of listed buildings, yes.	Same answer.	I don't know, maintenance is not my field of expertise. But I think that there is nothing more than operating budget.	Same answer.	In France, little awareness of what is a historic building. Buildings owners don't know (don't care) and don't turn toward themselves with the right people.		
48	The Netherlands	Central Europe	public authority	Business manager	Site/Project Management	No	No, I'm not a member of someone		Regulation	Sustainable building windows	2	2	No	Yes	Yes	Additional funding is possible when it is also a public use (like schools)	7	Restoration, including enhanced energy efficiency should be possible		
49	Ireland	Northern Europe	practitioners	Architect + Urban Designer	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of someone	ICOMOS Ireland and SICOC	Demand, finance and time	Balance between efficiency and embodied carbon	20th century buildings	Building regulations lag behind policy	4	Case studies	No	Repair or restoration only	Yes, modest grants for homes	No	Yes	No
50	UK	Northern Europe	practitioners	Engineer	Engineering and Construction	No	No, I'm not a member of someone		Cost and planning regulations in the UK	Not enough publicly known and advised people	4	Private homes	In the UK it is widely believed that planning is not widely understood. 2 and guidance about the planning regulations is lacking.	I do not know	In the UK, the ECC scheme pays for work to homes of good people	No	I don't know			

51	Italy	Southern Europe	academia	Professor	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of someone	The difficulties in introducing new energy saving and maintaining the original configuration and way of use	Usually, their approach is limited to verify the feasibility, without taking into account the specific configuration and way of use	4		The rules are too much generated as they were not thought for buildings built in different contexts and so on	Formation of specific courses	Historic Building Energy Retrofit ATLAS	only interventions which allow to improve the quality of the environment through the improvement of the energy efficiency	only interventions which allow to improve the quality of the environment through the improvement of the energy efficiency	In Italy there are	Sometimes, there are			
52	Ireland	Northern Europe	practitioners, academia	Architect Researcher	Architecture and Design	No	No, I'm not a member of someone	Professional training, limited workloads, lack of regulations, and no incentives to make a difference between existing buildings and historic buildings (and renovation work)	When is professional, but not about historic performance features as often they offer more knowledge about historic renovation work specific to the performance of historic buildings	4	There are good examples about historic buildings, but people spend short time there, more on renovation about historic buildings would be interesting as it doesn't require a lot of time there	consultatory regulations, lack of clarity about the level of intervention on the building and the building and its architectural value	Education, awareness programmes (DIT) - the historic building type is more the importance of the building, age of the building, and the conservation of the building and how they are connected, as well as their relevance would be very helpful	Built Heritage Investment Scheme support small to medium scale projects. The Historic Structures Fund (HSF) supports public and private buildings for the use of regional funds. A second option of the fund is for the preservation of building facades (windows, entrances, architectural details)	There are public funds for the installation of solar panels, as well as for lead pipes	I'm not aware of that					
53	Italy	Southern Europe	academia	Full Professor at the University of Genoa - Architecture and Design Department/Architecture	Academia and Research	No	Yes, I'm a member of someone	Italian Committee	Their architectural character, preferences, needs, and material and physical consistency	Current awareness and expertise about energy performance of historic buildings and the impact of ancient and modern masonry structures	1	when they propose abstract and conceptual for the construction of new buildings	Outlining technical aspects of any level of the building process and any involved administrative and technical involved organisations	NO	I do not know, I get the PSRR funds for the energy transition	Yes	Yes there are, few and difficult to obtain	Invest in knowledge, education and training of the involved professionals at any level and also of the entrepreneurs and workers			
54	Italy	Southern Europe	academia	Professor	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of someone	Making historic buildings more energy efficient faces several barriers. Preservation and aesthetic concerns often restrict interventions to maintain historic integrity. Changes must respect the original design appearance, looking options for modern upgrades. Structural and Material Limitations: Historic buildings are often characterised with fragile materials and non-standard techniques that complicate the	Energy retrofit of historic buildings often lack professionals with combined expertise in preservation and energy efficiency. Key skills needed include: Conservation Specialists or knowledge of historic preservation techniques to highlight historical features. Energy Auditors: Ability to assess energy performance and integrate it with historic preservation. Collaboration: Working with architects and energy experts. Skilled Craftpeople	1	Class Studies and Practicals	2	Public support for energy retrofit in historic buildings is insufficient. Lacking an integrated guidance, detailed case studies, manuals, incentives, specialised training programmes and regulatory measures for sharing expertise and experiences.	NO	I do not know about any specific support for historic buildings. Yes, it is possible for historic buildings, more without heating and ventilation heat recovery system. PV systems.	No	Yes, as far as I know	Yes, improvements are substantial	No		
55	Poland	Central Europe	academia	Researcher	Academia and Research	Yes	No, I'm not a member of someone	Limitations associated with acceptable historic modifications.	Understanding of the results and influence of the introduced changes upon the building and its components.	3	Qualified reports on condition of the historic buildings	Lack of strict regulatory and financial support	Specific requirements and technical support	No	I do not know about any specific support for historic buildings. Yes, it is possible for historic buildings, more without heating and ventilation heat recovery system. PV systems.	No	Yes, as far as I know	Yes, improvements are substantial	No		
56	UK	Northern Europe	public authority	Engagement manager	EU/Project Management	No	No, I'm not a member of someone	Cost, wide variety of service, uncertainty over longevity of technology	Ability to communicate clearly the risks, costs and implications	2	3	Simple energy-related guidance, practical information relating specifically to historic buildings	No	Not sure	Not sure	Not sure	Not sure	No			
57	USA	Northern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of someone	Lack of financial space for experimentation, reducing historic building at renovation and then.	Flexibility to historic experience	4	Historic doors and windows for restoration. In higher historic buildings, without compromising appearance	Most policies are developed and implemented based on what is possible in the contemporary construction market. We need more historic building. Better policy would be to encourage if well-developed for historic buildings industry	Current government support. We need more support for historic buildings. Better policy would be to encourage if well-developed for historic buildings industry	Yes, some US states have tax related based programs that historic buildings are often exempt from property tax that can not benefit from tax breaks	No	There is funding for repair of existing historic buildings, which varies by state but not specifically for historic buildings	The technology exists to reduce carbon to near zero in many existing buildings but is very expensive and there is no feasible payback period. This is the biggest barrier for non profits that are usually cash short. The US.				
58	Argentina	Southern Europe	Architect Professor	Architect	Academia and Research	No	Yes, I'm a member of someone	VP ISC20C	Knowledge	3	Very hard, public buildings	3	2	Education	Hbaratava	May be	Difficult	Very little	Just few	no	
59	Sweden	Northern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	Yes	No, I'm not a member of someone	Knowledge along priority areas, local professionals	LCA analysis, not methodologies to assess and compare environmental impact on heritage values and CO2 or energy balance	4	2	3	2	2	Practical methodology guides	Spara and Bevara, HSB/Rutias	All types	Not commonly	Yes	Yes	
60	North Macedonia	Southern Europe	public authority, practitioners	N/A	Other	No	Yes, I'm a member of someone	ICOMOS Macedonia	Professional skills, legal restrictions	4	2	2	2	4	No	No	No	Yes	No		
61	North Macedonia	Southern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of someone	ICOMOS Macedonia	Professional skills, legal restrictions	4	2	2	2	1	Educational	Southern Europe	No	No	No	Yes	/
62	France	Central Europe	academia	Researcher	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of someone	political will	Hydro behaviour and water combination	4	2	2	2	1	specific numerical tools	Yes any energy renovation needs	same answer - but other helps	more complex	able to repair	no	

61	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Southern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of some	Bosnia and Herzegovina (ISC20C)	Lack of knowledge	2 Creativity	Residential, 4 20th century architecture	3	2 Municipality, education	Yes, education	As previous	No				
62	Italy	Southern Europe	practitioners, academia	Research Fellow/Architect	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of some		There may be a number of barriers, w.o. historical, artistic and landscape, of the buildings, compatibility of solutions with respect to the construction and materials used in buildings, different architectural languages, incoherence and reversibility of solutions, lack of shared solutions for historic buildings, etc.	Lack of knowledge of the phenomenological behavior of a building, which may differ from new construction. Lack of knowledge of historic and specific solutions for such buildings, such as: preservation, intervention phase of the historic building, lack of shared solutions, etc.	2	2	2	Updated guidelines, easy and quick information	Allessia Buda, Conservazione ed efficienza energetica dell'edilizia storica, Napoli 2023	Optimize envelope insulation, window replacement, installation of technological systems (solar collectors, heat pumps, photovoltaics, building automation, etc.)	Yes, there is funding to subsidize the repair of existing buildings			
63	Estonia	Northern Europe	academia	Professor	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of some		A heritage conservation officer that understands natural sciences.	Heritage conservation 1 understanding of natural sciences.	Higher energy performance 4 and zero-emissions buildings	3	4	Showing that drastic improvement of energy building is possible	"Low carbon emission renovation of historical residential buildings" (https://www.enrconect.com/en/articles/619)	Yes, to all measures.	Yes, to all measures.	Less than energy retrofit. Therefore it is essential to involve building so that it requires small maintenance.	No without improvement of energy performance	Heritage authorities, Owner financial capability
64	UK	Northern Europe	public authority	Project Coordinator	Site/Project Management	No	No, I'm not a member of some		Building regulations (national and local), etc.	2 regulations and guidance that can be complex and difficult to navigate. There were people involved in UK construction in 2020-21, most in 1.5, 1.8, 1.9, 2.0 and 2.1 year ago	Higher energy performance 4 and zero-emissions buildings	3	4	Showing that drastic improvement of energy building is possible	https://www.enrconect.com/en/articles/619	Yes, to all measures.	Yes, to all measures.	Less than energy retrofit. Therefore it is essential to involve building so that it requires small maintenance.	No without improvement of energy performance	Heritage authorities, Owner financial capability
65	Belgium	Central Europe	practitioners	Architect - Research scientist	Architecture and Design	No	No, I'm not a member of some		I think that there is a lack of attention for restoration matters and that restoration is not sufficiently seen as a multi-criteria process.	3 A big picture	Higher energy performance 4 and zero-emissions buildings	3	4	Showing that drastic improvement of energy building is possible	https://www.enrconect.com/en/articles/619	Yes, to all measures.	Yes, to all measures.	Less than energy retrofit. Therefore it is essential to involve building so that it requires small maintenance.	No without improvement of energy performance	Heritage authorities, Owner financial capability
66	Portugal	Southern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	No	No, I'm not a member of some		I don't think that historic buildings have to be more energy efficient	3 historical, materials and passive solutions	Higher energy performance 4 and zero-emissions buildings	3	4	Showing that drastic improvement of energy building is possible	https://www.enrconect.com/en/articles/619	Yes, to all measures.	Yes, to all measures.	Less than energy retrofit. Therefore it is essential to involve building so that it requires small maintenance.	No without improvement of energy performance	Heritage authorities, Owner financial capability
67	Norway	Northern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of some	ICOFORIT	You have to change historic building materials of existing buildings, quality, to new ones with poor quality.	Calculation of energy retrofit date	3 single family housing	3	4	Showing that drastic improvement of energy building is possible	https://www.enrconect.com/en/articles/619	Yes, to all measures.	Yes, to all measures.	Less than energy retrofit. Therefore it is essential to involve building so that it requires small maintenance.	No without improvement of energy performance	Heritage authorities, Owner financial capability
68	Ireland	Northern Europe	academia	Researcher (social science)	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of some		regulations, lack of funding	3 historic buildings specifically	Higher energy performance 4 and zero-emissions buildings	3	4	Showing that drastic improvement of energy building is possible	https://www.enrconect.com/en/articles/619	Yes, to all measures.	Yes, to all measures.	Less than energy retrofit. Therefore it is essential to involve building so that it requires small maintenance.	No without improvement of energy performance	Heritage authorities, Owner financial capability
69	Poland	Central Europe	academia	Associate Professor	Academia and Research	Yes	No, I'm not a member of some		Difficulties in programming, saving, solutions that are cheaper to invest in	3	2	3	2	Showing that drastic improvement of energy building is possible	https://www.enrconect.com/en/articles/619	Yes, to all measures.	Yes, to all measures.	Less than energy retrofit. Therefore it is essential to involve building so that it requires small maintenance.	No without improvement of energy performance	Heritage authorities, Owner financial capability
70	UK	Northern Europe	academia	Associate Professor	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of some		Lack of guidance	3	2	3	2	Showing that drastic improvement of energy building is possible	https://www.enrconect.com/en/articles/619	Yes, to all measures.	Yes, to all measures.	Less than energy retrofit. Therefore it is essential to involve building so that it requires small maintenance.	No without improvement of energy performance	Heritage authorities, Owner financial capability

71	Belgium	Central Europe	public authority, practitioners	Conservation Specialist	Cultural Heritage Professionals	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICOMOS Belgium and ISCZC	architectural quality of the building, the legislation is not enforced, lack of subsidies	feasibility is necessary in itself, but it has to be protected as heritage, and currently being compared with one heritage project. I'm not an expert in the field and the knowledge of historic and technical aspects and solutions with heritage evaluation on top of criteria.	La Cité Moderne (Berthelme) built by Victor Bourgeois in 1920s, protected as heritage, and currently being compared with one heritage project. I'm not an expert in the field and the knowledge of historic and technical aspects and solutions with heritage evaluation on top of criteria.	La Cité Moderne (Berthelme) built by Victor Bourgeois in 1920s, protected as heritage, and currently being compared with one heritage project. I'm not an expert in the field and the knowledge of historic and technical aspects and solutions with heritage evaluation on top of criteria.	too strong movements in architecture in Belgium. I'm not an expert in the field and the knowledge of historic and technical aspects and solutions with heritage evaluation on top of criteria.	4. I'm not an expert in the field and the knowledge of historic and technical aspects and solutions with heritage evaluation on top of criteria.	www.postweldingmaterials.be/https://www.barnet2020.eu/about.html/https://www.aef.be/https://www.innovacione.eu/innovacione.com	mainly subsidies (national and regional), funding for insulation, sun panels, collective housing with heritage status, yes but not enough	yes but enough	probably the main issue is near future and mainly regarding more architectural productions	
72	Poland	Central Europe	practitioners, academia	Architect, Urban Designer, Researcher	Architecture and Design	Yes	No, I'm not a member of ICOMOS	protection of the form and function, the historical value, the architectural quality, the innovative, they are not allowed to try anything, long time of permit receiving	basic knowledge of the possibilities of retrofit solutions, weak knowledge of technical aspects, lack of knowledge of historic and technical aspects and solutions with heritage evaluation on top of criteria.	2	2	the progress of the process, the knowledge of the possibilities of retrofit solutions, weak knowledge of technical aspects, lack of knowledge of historic and technical aspects and solutions with heritage evaluation on top of criteria.	2	The Sandover Foundation publications	I have basic knowledge	Yes, the solutions are publicly announced. E.g. the photovoltaic solar panels, the use of the building, the government, the local government	not for private users	Only for high class monuments
73	Germany	Central Europe	academia	Physicist	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMOS	Adaptation of the retrofit to the historic value	special treatment of the possibilities of retrofit solutions, weak knowledge of technical aspects, lack of knowledge of historic and technical aspects and solutions with heritage evaluation on top of criteria.	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
74	Estonia	Northern Europe	academia	Associated Professor	Academia and Research	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICOMOS Estonia	lack of post intervention effect, the role in management	Heritage experts have lot of skills, but project managers for efficiency projects lack experience	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
75	Italy	Southern Europe	academia	University Lecturer	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMOS	conservation constraints	knowledge of historic conservation constraints	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	3
76	Estonia	Northern Europe	public authority, practitioners	Project manager of LIFE heritage/CME	Site/Project Management	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICOMOS Estonia	1. Funding, 'to cover the cost of. Sub, energy efficiency improvements are a challenge of culturally heritage details. 2. Lack of knowledge of historic and technical aspects and solutions with heritage evaluation on top of criteria. 3. Exposure paper work, what it comes heritage buildings.	Energy audits that have brought about sufficient energy efficiency improvements. 2. While the knowledge of historic and technical aspects and solutions with heritage evaluation on top of criteria. 3. Exposure paper work, what it comes heritage buildings.	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	3
77	Switzerland	Central Europe	academia	Historian	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMOS	The main challenge is making historic buildings more energy efficient, technical challenges, aesthetic considerations, and preservation. The main challenge is making historic buildings more energy efficient, technical challenges, aesthetic considerations, and preservation.	The main challenge is making historic buildings more energy efficient, technical challenges, aesthetic considerations, and preservation. The main challenge is making historic buildings more energy efficient, technical challenges, aesthetic considerations, and preservation.	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3

78	Switzerland	Central Europe	public authority, practitioners	heritage conservator, architect, writer	Cultural Heritage Professionals	No	Yes, I'm a member of Icomos	Switzerland	Each historic building has its own specific characteristics. A new building is generally different from a historic building in terms of energy efficiency. Currently, energy efficiency assessments are calculated on an element-by-element basis and do not take into account the actual consumption. This method of calculation puts historic buildings at a high disadvantage.	There is often a lack of understanding of the existing construction and materials.	There is a lack of awareness in ordinary historic buildings.	has the cost of legal requirements is too high for owners.	4	3	No	Yes, for measures measures	In Switzerland, these policies vary from canton to canton in terms of public funding is granted for non-habitat buildings.	Yes in Geneva.	In Geneva, public subsidies are available for the repair of existing historic residential buildings.	No	
79	Turkey	Southern Europe	practitioners	Architect/Engineer	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of Icomos	ICOMOS Turkey / ICOMOSAI / ICOMOP	Restorators not aware of the thermal transmittance of the materials they use.	1) knowledge on construction materials and methods	A historic building is hard to keep its initial appearance after renovation.	1	1	No	the owners of the houses need to be aware of the energy efficiency benefits.	https://www.turkey.com.tr/en/energy-efficiency	No.	No.	No.	N/A	N/A
80	UK	Northern Europe	practitioners, academia	Building Services Engineer (MEP)	Engineering and Construction	No	No, I'm not a member of Icomos		Funding, agreement, general public lack of PH, lack of guidance	5 I think we are still a bit far away from fully understanding our historic buildings and how to work with them. We also lack of understanding of the building fabric.	Well recorded 1) good projects including PCE	When there's a need, we have to understand that some historic buildings might have a level of energy efficiency due to many factors	Building guide 1) for historic buildings. No, but I think this would be useful and personally would love to help building one	It's very difficult with heritage issues - public buildings have better resources. Maybe Depends on the purpose of the building and funding provider. As there are no real social issues to address and these might gain priority	Yes, but I think they are very often running on their own terms and are often not really applying as they don't understand the requirements of it and the consequences of certain buildings coverage would also have funding access affected.	No	No	No	No	No	
81	France	Central Europe	practitioners	R&D Director	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of Icomos		Knowledge on technical solutions and lack of product	1	1	2	2								
82	UK	Northern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	No	No, I'm not a member of Icomos		Lack of funding, lack of knowledge and awareness	Understanding of historic buildings, breathability	Sensitive and 4 historic examples	Professionals do not seem to understand the historical significance of old properties.	3	3	No	Yes, limited sources	As above	Don't know	Don't know	No	
83	France	Central Europe	public authority, practitioners	Local Urban Planner	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of Icomos	Spain	Costs associated especially to heritage. Lack of technical know-how amongst architects, engineers and builders. Lack of technical performance data in most major buildings. Identification of heritage buildings and restrictive regulations. Lack of assistance to individual owners as well as joint ones (cooperatives)	Knowledge about heritage conservation comprises with current specifications, identification needs for historic and traditional buildings	Cost-effective solutions 2) projects and financing 3) multi-ownership residential buildings	Approved 1) minimum can maximum can justify the architectural expression of buildings.	Project set-up 2) identification of buildings 3) analysis and 4) understanding of heritage significance by building professionals (not heritage professionals)	Yes, for the diagnostic and measures	Yes, for the diagnostic and measures	No	Yes, there is more funding for existing buildings that for new ones	There is a lack of data on the performance of historic buildings, their energy ratings does not add to the memory on level experience. EU energy ratings are not able to measure and understand historic buildings. In the same context as France, in France, the cost of energy retrofit of older buildings is having poorer residents out of historic districts and buildings.			
84	Czech Republic	Central Europe	academia	Architectural Historian	Academia and Research	No	Yes, I'm a member of Icomos	Czech NLC, ICOMOS, CIVIVI, ThaqPhilos	If "historic" means "historic", there is not enough of traditional last (brick, cast)	2	Buildings made of brick in cold climate 3) "historic" buildings with great facades	3	3	1	Yes, the governmental grant (in Czechia) for a "patrimonium" measure.						
85	France	Central Europe	public authority, practitioners	Research Engineer	Engineering and Construction	No	No, I'm not a member of Icomos		Efficient technical solution that preserve heritage value	2	examples of building that have been 2) retrofit and then monitored to prove their energy efficiency		2								
86	UK	Northern Europe	practitioners	Traditional Builder	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of Icomos		Incorrect advice given to building owners. Budget. Lack of understanding from building owners and comes to a historic buildings	Misunderstand 2) build structures and the use of materials	Domestic buildings e.g 3) small houses in historic areas.	There must be a clear distinction 3) between old and newly well constructed material use	The information is not there but often given by architects, designers and local authority	Unclear	unclear	unclear	unclear				
87	Switzerland	Central Europe	practitioners	Engineer	Engineering and Construction	No	No, I'm not a member of Icomos		Lack of knowledge of existing local products, lack of expertise on energy from authorities, technical procedures.	Above all, a lack of knowledge of different types of buildings and energy from products (roofs, walls, etc.)	A database of different types of buildings and energy from products (roofs, walls, etc.)	long tedious procedures, 3) different types of buildings, the right tools and the right products	Yes, Building envelope improvement, heating replacement, modernization of production systems (DPA / www.fancenergy.ch)	Probably on a case-by-case basis as the various countries (DPA / www.fancenergy.ch)	Probably on a case-by-case basis as the various countries (DPA / www.fancenergy.ch)						

08 Czech Republic	Central Europe	practitioners	Village Planner, Preservationist	Cultural Heritage Professionals	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICOMOS	ICOMOS, ICOMOS	Orientation of the market and competition of new buildings, projects and material.	1 Multidisciplinary expertise.	Unconventional measures based on: 2. historic-based solutions, use of natural materials, etc.	Preference for modern measures to improve policy building in municipalities.	Construction and material-friendly approach in preservation of historic values.	Yes, e.g. https://liberalize.eu/article/	Yes, most support areas (thermal insulation, energy conservation, energy adaptation, and mitigation and mitigation measures) provided the necessary support for professionals in the sector is not enough. There are best practice databases of courses, but are unusable (databases of solutions (libraries of courses)).	Yes, most support areas (thermal insulation, energy conservation, energy adaptation, and mitigation and mitigation measures) provided the necessary support for professionals in the sector is not enough. There are best practice databases of courses, but are unusable (databases of solutions (libraries of courses)).	No, there is no funding for regular maintenance.	Yes, but only in the case of the listed cultural movement outside the territory of municipalities. It often leads to misadaptation in practice.	Misadaptation, loss of historical value and expression.
09 UK	Northern Europe	practitioners	Heritage Conservation	Cultural Heritage Professionals	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMOS		Understanding of traditional building fabric and materials and how they manage as and measure them)	1) Condition assessments, 2) building trades with professional methods, 3) 3) identifying sympathetic projects to end communicate measures to work with the existing building	Need good examples across a wide range of typologies, as well as progress level of retrofit	Publics often encourage single-measure solutions which creates negative feedback loops to reduce the appropriateness of the measures. Quality checks are often lacking	General guidance is often too generic for professionals in the sector is not enough. There are best practice databases of courses, but are unusable (databases of solutions (libraries of courses)).	No / sometimes	No / sometimes	No / sometimes	No / sometimes	The best place to spend spend money in this space is likely to be in the upfront investment. The more that is known about a building at project conception, the more likely the better the outcomes.	
10 UK	Northern Europe	practitioners	Chartered Surveyor	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMOS		Cost and confidence in the measures available	Survey and assessment of what is available to do the work	Domestic scale, simple interventions, typology 9	It is often the perceptions of domestic policy are not always appropriate.	Examples of upgrades work by building typology 9	Historic Environment Scotland Publications/publication_type=95	Yes, but only perceptions of wider repair materials, and public awareness	Yes, but measures are generally modern systems that are not always technically appropriate.	No	Yes, but only on publicly accessible buildings, generally not private ones.	Building fabric upgrades is only one part of the plant and equipment is a significant factor and often as expensive (and not always long lasting either...)
11 UK	Northern Europe	practitioners	Architect	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICOMOS		Knowledge	1. Interest in workmanship	Windows & Doors, 1. Elements and terraces	1 VASTH	1 Every kind	EWHT etc.	Sometimes, for studies	Difficult	No	Sometimes	
12 Italy	Southern Europe	academia	Researcher	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMOS		Interventions on historic buildings	2	2	1	1						
13 Estonia	Northern Europe	public authority	Products Manager	Site/Project Management	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMOS		EU directives, domestic rules of law but also related to buildings	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
16 Italy	Southern Europe	academia	Full Professor, University of Ferrara	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMOS		The projects that I do as a historic building, there are also technologies used for interventions without losing its historical value and without unsustainable interventions costs	Skills that create the identification of the most appropriate intervention energy resources (especially in winter) examples with thermal insulation with thermally breakable windows and without vapour barrier, examples illustrating the possibility of working on listed historic buildings, and thus the absence of a targeted scientific and economic incentives.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
17 Italy	Southern Europe	academia	Professor (University)	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMOS		preservation of historic and features	energy efficiency 2. solutions, ability to solve in context	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
18 Estonia	Northern Europe	practitioners	Built heritage adviser	Cultural Heritage Professionals	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICOMOS	ICOMOS Estonia	Main barrier is the lacking knowledge of the owners how to build historic building more energy efficient without disturbing the cultural values. Also the bureaucracy and restrictions on renovation of the buildings of cultural value. Not enough skilled experts (engineers, architects) who could help owners with the matters that come from energy efficient.	Knowledge about that 1) retrofit solutions for the historic house of cultural value, 2) renovation of the cultural value has been kept	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	

99	UK	Northern Europe	practitioners	Chartered Engineer	Engineering and Construction	No	No, I'm not a member of Icoms	Lack of correct technology use or assets that are inappropriate	Few people that understand older buildings which will lead to mistakes	1 hour old audio wall buildings work	Encouraging technologies instead of waiting for governments to make decisions. Encouraging politicians	More understanding of the fact that I realise can be made and you search you can find it but nobody bothers	Very few grants are available and what there are are spent on obscure works	Yes for some insulation if on social measures	No	No	The use of hydrogen must be encouraged	
100	UK	Northern Europe	public authority	Management Consultant	SaI/Project Management	No	No, I'm not a member of Icoms	Planning restrictions, ability shortages, mismanagement.	Traditional joinery, working with time-based regulations, masonry, lead and zinc work.	Effective use of heat pumps in old buildings with high ceilings.	Refusal to allow modern materials, constraints on resources, limited use of fittings in listed buildings. Focus on much focus on a replacement window, lack of capacity and expertise on old buildings in planning departments.	Fact: There is a lot of contradictory information out there and inconsistent decisions. It is really worth insulating walls on a stone house with walls that three feet thick? Will it be worth insulating floors? Will an air source heat pump be possible on old buildings? Will it be worth building a Georgian house?	There should be a standard set of UK on retrofitting old buildings but if we have to have to pay 20% more, we should be able to do it. These are grants available for replacement windows.	Not that I know of	I don't know	The energy rating system is not appropriate for old buildings and needs reform.		
101	UK	Northern Europe	retired doctor	Other	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of Icoms	Cost and planning restrictions	3	3 small domestic buildings	restrictions on double glazing and insulation of older panels	1 Financial	no	not sure	very little	no	a little for repair	
102	UK	Northern Europe	practitioners	Architect, energy and sustainability consultant	Architecture and Design	Yes	No, I'm not a member of Icoms	There are many old buildings with technical knowledge (especially of masonry-based tasks), cost, lack of specialist support, etc.	Understanding professionals are sufficient skills. It's not many do, but they can be trained.	2 Examples related to UK heritage types.	Not all UK local planning officers and historic buildings. Architects can balance heritage issues and the retrofit needs. There is plenty of guidance and resources such as PAS 2023 and PAS 2028. There has been some very good work on this under the PROTECT project at King's College London University in London, which is a joint project with University College London and PAS 2023. There has also been a lot of work on this issue by the UK Sustainable Traditional Buildings Alliance (UKSTBA) and the Historic Buildings Council (HBC).	In the UK, yes, mostly for listed buildings. In the UK, yes, for nearly all listed buildings. In the UK, there is no funding for repairs - that is a task left to building owners.	No - that is left to building owners.	In the UK, there is no funding for repairs - that is a task left to building owners.	More public awareness of the need to retrofit buildings is essential. The case is being made by electricity and heat pump companies promoting heat pumps as a panacea without the need for significant insulation to reduce demand.			
103	UK	Northern Europe	retired	Other	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of Icoms	Cost, who is a trustee professional	I really don't know whether professionals have sufficient skills. It's not many do, but they can be trained.	1 How would we know?	I don't think these are really 1 constraints in the planning process	1 Publicity	Not aware	Same as above.	Don't know but suspect not.	Don't know		
104	Spain	Southern Europe	practitioners	Sustainable Energy Technician	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of Icoms	POCTIF EU Project	Historic buildings need very specific technologies and materials that are not known to the regular companies	2 integrated and related in historic buildings	The policies do not take into account the new technologies, the professionals in the market do not have the knowledge of integration of historic buildings and are not trained in energy efficiency and heritage	We are far of a proper support. There is a need of better knowledge of integration of historic buildings and are not trained in energy efficiency and heritage	Probably not, I do not know any funding schemes for maintenance costs. It would be more an economic scheme such as EDCI companies or something like that	Similar to previous answer	Not now			
105	UK	Northern Europe	practitioners, academia	Built Heritage Planner	Cultural Heritage Professionals	No	Yes, I'm a member of Icoms	Financial cost (upst term), and property markets reporting need not quality of outcome	2 Most	3 environments of historic and heritage driven nature	2 No examples I can give	4 Guidance is adequate	Not aware	Not that I am aware of but there may be	Not that I am aware of but there may be	Not that I am aware of and unlikely to be the case	Not that I am aware of but unlikely	Disincentivise the use of unsustainable materials, EG through taxation, and vice versa
106	Norway	Northern Europe	practitioners, academia, public authorities	Chief Scientist in climate adaptation of buildings	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of Icoms	lack of skills and available cost efficient solutions. Historic buildings and materials that promote such.	4	2 (technology, materials, services), but also regarding neighborhood scale	2	economic support	Partly energy related to not available equipment (PV, heatpumps etc). Other there across our private see also next question	Consultancies and technical equipment (PV, heatpumps etc). Other there across our private see also next question	See above "Eknow" for new and existing buildings			
107	Poland	Central Europe	practitioners	Architect, researcher	Architecture and Design	Yes	No, I'm not a member of Icoms	I think the main barriers are tied to the cost of materials and labour required to use solutions that are compatible with preserving heritage while ensuring energy efficiency and the general competitiveness to provide them by private companies.	LCA, post-occupancy evaluation, EQ and ESG measurement	3 (culture of a long-term, but to make the project cost-effective)	3	I do not know of any such database apart from HBE/Hatlas/HBEH	Ongoing maintenance that consists of small works is not funded in any way. Buildings are considered a form of "major" maintenance costs and they are subsidised.	Repair is subsidised, and thermal retrofit can sometimes be equated with repair	The main barrier in Poland is that energy efficiency is considered not-essential when dealing with heritage, so things like the overall technical condition and usability of listed buildings are seen as extra pressing. We just not at that level yet, economically and socially.			

114	UK	Northern Europe	practitioners	Community climate and retrofit activist	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of Isonics	<p>I say when I talk with standards for retrofit and energy efficiency in retro, as there is a lot of work to do. Planning restrictions related buildings and conservation areas in the UK. Availability of solutions like the intervention. Some operational emissions and costs, against full life-cycle carbon emissions. In building in just retrofitting long term. But there is not (and) any obligation (or a culture) to</p>	<p>Understanding of conservation issues for buildings and case studies. Awareness of high-tech improvement.</p>	1	Edinburgh pre 1915 tenement flat buildings.	3	<p>Financial support. Encouragement to invest more upfront to reduce operational emissions. There has been occasional support available from the Edinburgh from the Heritage 'Climate Emergency Grant'.</p>	unknown	There has been occasional support available from the Edinburgh from the Heritage 'Climate Emergency Grant'.	I don't think so.	Scottish Gov grants only support new measures.	People need to be educated (required?) to maintain that building, want to see more on-site maintenance and retrofit planning and implementation as a continuum. There is a priority to much more focus on retrofit, as if it's something independent from repair and maintenance, and can be tackled separately.		
115	France	Central Europe	academia	Architectural Historian	Academia and Research	No	Yes, I'm a member of Isonics	FRANCE, ISONICS	Lack of knowledge and information, combined with pressure of the regulatory framework.	As an architectural historian, I don't have the ability to answer this question.	3	As an architectural historian, I don't have the ability to answer this question.	As an architectural historian, I don't have the ability to answer this question.	1	no	As an architectural historian, I don't have the ability to answer this question.	As an architectural historian, I don't have the ability to answer this question.	As an architectural historian, I don't have the ability to answer this question.	no	
116	Sweden	Northern Europe	academia	Associate Professor	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of Isonics	Cost		4	4	<p>Contradicting 2 measurements. 1. Economic assessment</p>	2	Economic support						
117	Sweden	Northern Europe	practitioners	Sustainability consultant within architecture	Architecture and Design	No	No, I'm not a member of Isonics		<p>I think both research and skills on how to balance between the historic values and energy efficiency. The building has been renovated on new full or easy to change a window that is not meeting building technical solutions (insulation, etc.)</p>	<p>Knowledge within the sector, combined with professional consultants and historical and technical expertise on a</p>	4	<p>I think both research and skills on how to balance between the historic values and energy efficiency. The building has been renovated on new full or easy to change a window that is not meeting building technical solutions (insulation, etc.)</p>	3	<p>Innovative renovations using old knowledge and materials, was a more holistic approach based on cultural heritage. 3 compliance combined with building practice research group. New knowledge and conservation of architectural values as well - what one experience in a team</p>	1	<p>Not without a lot of effort and not without - there might be different calls but no systematic support, see earlier answer.</p>	<p>To some extent if research is involved.</p>	<p>Not without a lot of effort and not without - there might be different calls but no systematic support, see earlier answer.</p>	No systematic support	no
118	UK	Northern Europe	retired	Other	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of Isonics		<p>The scale of the problem to retrofit our built-up historic city like London is such that there are many different types of problems in the need to invest</p>	3	<p>Currently it is clear possible to retrofit older buildings on a case-by-case basis. Edinburgh World Heritage 2. Like in Cambridge they have been King's Chapel, one of the most iconic buildings in the country. Why the inconsistency?</p>	1	<p>No sufficient to address the demand.</p>	<p>No sufficient to address the demand.</p>						
119	UK	Northern Europe	public authority	Local Authority Worker	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of Isonics	<p>Cost. Lack of traditional skills, lack of maintenance and repair</p>	<p>conservation specialist 3 conservation skills, problems and interventions</p>	4	<p>retail at the domestic scale, small scale, 2 interventions that provide flexibility for individual homeowners</p>	4	<p>the guidance is often either too specialist or too generic - encouraging a whole range of approaches that may not be suited to the buildings in question</p>	<p>various Scottish government grants for heat pumps and solar panels</p>	<p>not aware of any but is needed</p>	<p>not aware of any but is needed</p>	<p>the primary barrier is the current condition of the historic building stock in the country. For too much investment to be placed on intervention measures that are not necessary until the building is in a good condition - the application of these measures while the building is in a state of disrepair could damage the long term health of the building leading to greater problems in the future.</p>			
120	UK	Northern Europe	academia	Technologist	Other	No	No, I'm not a member of Isonics	<p>Historic preservation based on building objectives are often conflicting with environmental objectives. Identifying and the historic building stock. Upgrading historic buildings, and the historic building stock. Identifying and the historic building stock. Upgrading historic buildings, and the historic building stock. Identifying and the historic building stock. Upgrading historic buildings, and the historic building stock.</p>	<p>Other and related building objectives are often conflicting with environmental objectives. Identifying and the historic building stock. Upgrading historic buildings, and the historic building stock. Identifying and the historic building stock. Upgrading historic buildings, and the historic building stock.</p>	3	<p>Conservation retrofits, retrofit 3 of private multi-residential buildings in an area.</p>	2	<p>Outlets the opposite in the UK. Retrofitting is subject to a lot of development in it. There are some funding but it requires only the services of a government approved architectural installer. This is a generalised uplift in fee for historic buildings, some of which could be hard to conserve the great. In a building that is not suitable on smaller projects to have a separate architectural assessment within the main contract.</p>	<p>Yes, see previous.</p>	<p>No</p>					
121	Spain	Southern Europe	practitioners	Master Ingeniero de Caminos Canales y Puertos	Engineering and Construction	No	No, I'm not a member of Isonics	<p>Las viviendas medianas y pequeñas de las ciudades</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>Modulos de rehabilitacion 1. Conservacion de patrimonio edificado del edificio</p>	<p>Programa de rehabilitacion 2. Conservacion de patrimonio edificado del edificio</p>	<p>Programa de rehabilitacion 2. Conservacion de patrimonio edificado del edificio</p>	<p>no</p>	<p>no</p>	<p>no</p>	<p>no</p>	<p>no</p>	<p>Programas equivalentes a los edificios residenciales para todos los casos</p>		

147	UK	Northern Europe	practitioners	Builder	Engineering and Construction	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMA	Conflict between planning restrictions and building control restrictions	Lack of understanding about what basic and realistic house warm.	1 Georgian townhouse	Draft proofing windows. Double glazing windows. At the same time I've worked for windows and leads to double glazing	We have worked on ordinary residential building for 20 years, I probably over 100. We have never had any contact with Historic Scotland or similar.	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Not aware of any. Used to be val help	Val rates back to 0% would be a start.
148	Belgium	Central Europe	practitioners	Engineer-Architect	Engineering and Construction	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMA	Financial, legal (long course of proceedings to obtain permits, sharing energy sources, ...)	holistic view on renovations and the focus on aesthetic measures that are not always compatible with the financial context. underrated - not fully understood - and having real problems when installing from the inside.	2 How to renovate a family dwelling with a reasonable budget?	Focus on the initial quality of buildings in a town. Lack of regulation that encourage shared energy services.	In Belgium: national subsidy schemes, depending on the region you're building in, located in energy labelling. different subsidies in different regions. Aligning these subsidy schemes and benchmarks based on climate zones (even on a European level) could enhance large renovation schemes.	yes, for renovating the building envelope (depending on the energy audit that is obtained through renovation), for PV installations (energy independency)	yes, for renovating the building envelope (depending on the energy audit that is obtained through renovation), for PV installations (energy independency)	only new measures	Aligning these subsidy schemes and benchmarks based on climate zones, European level, could enhance large renovation schemes.	
149	UK	Northern Europe	academia	Lecturer	Academia and Research	No	No, I'm not a member of ICOMA	Supply chain, quality of service provided	Understanding the consequences associated with each intervention, and the consequences of appropriate insulation	2 Long term performance of energy efficient public buildings	4 Maybe there is too much guidance. There is a need for more practical guidance across the different organisations	Funding in the UK is primarily for social housing (new or not)	no	no			
150	Greece	Southern Europe	practitioners	Architect and Consultant	Architecture and Design	No	Yes, I'm a member of ICOMA			2	1	1	1				
		Northern Europe		Architecture and Design													
		Central Europe		Academia and Research													
		Southern Europe		Engineering and Construction													
				Cultural Heritage Professionals													
				City/Project Management													
				Other													

Annex 3 – WP1 Interviews – Complete List of Interview Questions

List of interview questions used for FuturHist Work Package 1

Abbreviations: PRA: Practitioner, PUB: Public Authority, PRO: Professional Owner, PRI: Private Owner

Question ID	Interview question	PRA	PUB	PRO	PRI
QROLE	What is your professional role in relation to energy retrofit of historic buildings? For how long have you been working in the field?	x	x	x	
QBARRIER	What are the main barriers to making historic buildings more energy efficient?	x	x	x	x
QTECH	Barriers can be divided into technical, regulatory, financial and social. Can you think of any technical barriers, and how important would they be? Technical barriers are challenges related to the specific needs of historic buildings because of their construction and the materials used. It can also be lack of competence regarding such needs.	x	x	x	x
QREG	Can you think of any regulatory barriers, and how important would they be? Regulatory barriers are related to policies in different sectors, as well as lack of information to stakeholders regarding such policies.	x	x	x	x
QECON	Can you think of any economic barriers, and how important would they be? Economic barriers are challenges to make energy retrofit projects financially viable for historic buildings.	x	x	x	x
QSOCIAL	Can you think of any social barriers, and how important would they be? Social barriers are related to attitudes and awareness related to energy retrofit in historic buildings.	x	x	x	x
QTARGET	FuturHist deals with the energy retrofit of historic buildings, what do you think about current renovation rate? Are we going to meet national/european targets?	x	x	x	
QPOLICY	How well does current policy related to energy retrofit work in practice? What are strengths and weaknesses with current policies?	x	x	x	x
QEXEMPT	There is a possibility in the EPBD to exempt listed historic buildings from demands on energy efficiency. What do you think about this option?	x	x	x	x
QSUST1	Can current policies on energy efficiency hinder other dimensions of sustainability?	x	x		
QSUST2	If yes, what can be done to avoid negative effects on other sustainability dimensions?	x	x		
QIMPROVE	In sum, what do you think could be improved at the level of policy-making regarding energy retrofit of historic buildings?	x	x		

QGUIDE	Are there guidelines/standards for the overall planning process of energy retrofit in historic buildings? How are they used?	x	x	x	
QASSESS	How are energy retrofit projects in historic buildings generally assessed? (both before and after implementation)	x	x	x	
QMONITOR	What is generally monitored in retrofit projects? What stages (before, during, after?) Do you have internal routines/guidelines?	x	x	x	
QREASONS	Have you done any major renovation in your building(s) in recent years? What was the main reasons for the renovation?			x	x
QPLANNING	Do you plan any major renovation in your building(s)? What are the main reasons?			x	x
QEE	What have you done to make your building(s) more energy efficient? Do you have plans for future actions?			x	x
QPRA1	Which guidelines/standards, tools/software, practices do you use for the different steps in the planning process as described below?	x			
QPRA2	Are there any guidelines/tools that you would like to be developed?	x			
QPRO1	Do you know of any case where the protection of heritage values came into conflict with aspirations of energy efficiency? Can you describe the case and how it unfolded?			x	
QPRI1	Why is it important to save energy in your building (if you think so)?				x
QPRI2	Have your ambitions to make the building more energy efficient come into conflict with the preservation of heritage values?				x
QPRI3	Are you aware of any subsidies that are relevant for the energy retrofit of historic buildings (in particular for HBs)? Can you get subsidies for energy efficiency measures? Have you applied for such subsidies?				x
QPRI4	Do you know where you could go to find good advice?				x
QPRI5	Is there any any kind or information (guidelines, best practice, etc) that you are missing (in relation to energy retrofit).				x
QPRI6	What do you monitor (IEQ, energy use) in your building? What stages (before, during, after?)				x
QPRI7	How do you use the monitoring data?				x
QPRI8	Would you like to monitor more and if so, why?				x
QLAST	This was the last question. Is there anything you would like to add (related to the themes we have discussed?)	x	x	x	x

Annex 4 - WP1 Interviews - Practitioner form

Form to be filled by practitioners regarding guidelines/tools

Step	Guideline/standard	Tool (software etc.)	When
Heritage value assessment			
Pros/cons			
Assessment of the use of the building			
Pros/cons			
Condition survey and technical documentation			
Pros/cons			
Energy performance assessment			
Pros/cons			
Indoor environmental assessment			
Pros/cons			
Economic viability (e.g. LCC)			
Pros/cons			
Environmental impact (e.g. LCA, waste)			
Pros/cons			

Annex 5 - WP1 Interviews – Detailed analysis of feedback provided through practitioner forms

Heritage value assessment

Step	Guideline/standard	Tool (software etc.)	When
Heritage value assessment (6 respondents)	<p>There is a strong consensus that heritage conservation legislation/standards are the main guidelines/standards or databases used for heritage value assessment. They are developed at different level: international (e.g. Venice Charter, The Athens Charter for the Restoration of Historic Monuments) for 3 respondents (Spain, Poland, and Sweden), national for 4 respondents (2 in Spain, 1 in Poland, and 1 in Sweden), regional (e.g. Andalucia) or local (city level).</p> <p>Other pieces of legislation were mentioned: environmental legislation (European and national level), construction/planning legislation (national level).</p> <p>Professional practice/processes/methods at national level (e.g. conservation</p>	<p>Consensus amongst 3 respondents (Spain, Poland and Sweden) on the need to implement the task to study the history of the building and its context and to carry out a site visit (Spain, Poland, Sweden). In both cases, no specific tool was mentioned.</p> <p>2 respondents (UK and Sweden) mentioned the need to implement the task to analysis of the significance of the building, but no specific tool was mentioned.</p> <p>2 respondents (Spain, Poland)) mentioned the tools (databases/software), managed by local/regional/national authorities, that compile, provide access to and enable the visualisation of data on historic buildings (e.g. monument/historic buildings</p>	<p>Clear consensus amongst 6 respondents (3 in Spain, 1 in UK, 1 in Poland and 1 Sweden) that this step should take place at the beginning of the retrofit process (either at pre-design stage or at the start of the design phase)</p> <p>1 respondent also mentioned that the heritage value assessment should also take place happening at a more advanced point in the design - i.e. the building permit stage (when a planning permission/listed building consent is sought from a city council or local authority).</p>

	<p>statement in UK or Kulturhistoriska värdering av bebyggelse/Cultural-historical evaluation of the buildings in Sweden) to analyse historic significance were also mentioned.</p>	<p>registry/geoportal). This could be also considered as an external resource.</p> <p>2 respondents mentioned the tools used to create drawings (e.g. Polycam, Autocad).</p> <p>One respondent said he did not use any tool.</p>	
<p>Pros/cons</p>	<p>Accessibility of heritage conservation legislation/standards was mentioned as an advantage whilst the difficulty to adapt them to individual buildings was seen as a disadvantage (mentioned by 2 respondents).</p> <p>Other advantages mentioned for heritage conservation legislation/standards: well-integrated system, the fact there are international standards, clear legal framework, protection of the character, appearance and aesthetic of assets.</p> <p>Other disadvantages mentioned for heritage conservation legislation/standards: they limit or prevent retrofit interventions; it is a time-consuming documentation process.</p>		

	There were more advantages mentioned than disadvantages.		
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Assessment of the use of the building

Step	Guideline/standard	Tool (software etc.)	When
Assessment of the use of the building <i>(6 respondents)</i>	<p>There was potentially a problem with the wording of the question - as one respondent said he was not sure to understand the question.</p> <p>Some respondents seem to have adopted a holistic approach to answering the assessment of use - considering structural survey to probably define what type of loads (applied to the building structure) and activities can be acceptable in a given building.</p> <p>A respondent said it was not the architect's responsibility to assess the use of the building and that it was done before the design phase.</p> <p>The intent of the question was to focus on the assessment of the historic/future use of the building. It seems that some respondents understood it.</p>	<p>The feedback is quite diverse and touched on various aspects.</p> <p>1 respondent said that it is not the architect's responsibility.</p> <p>1 respondent mentioned the tools to engage with users and collect users feedback (e.g. in-house Home Standard Tool) and the tools to understand the use of the building by users (e.g. heat maps).</p> <p>2 respondents (Spain and Poland) mentioned the task to carry out structural tests, 1 respondent the task to carry out a site visit, 1 respondent the task of gathering/analysing historical documentation on the building, and 1 respondent mentioned the task to carry out consultation, engagement events outside the building, door to door with residents, and resident meetings. In all these instances, no specific tool was</p>	<p>Consensus on timing amongst 3 respondents (1 in Spain, 1 in UK, 1 in Poland) that this step should take place at the beginning of the retrofit process (either at pre-design stage or at the start of the design phase)</p>

	<p>Strong consensus on the need to refer to construction/planning legislation/standards at national level (3 respondents) and heritage conservation standards at international (2 respondents) and national level (1 respondent).</p>	<p>mentioned. 1 respondent mentioned technical expertise - which is rather a skill.</p>	
<p>Pros/cons</p>	<p>2 respondents (Poland and Spain) found that the structural requirements are very well defined (existing guidelines/standards (presumably in construction/planning legislation/standards). 1 respondent felt that existing legislation/standards provides a comprehensive approach.</p> <p>However, it was felt that the legislation/standards are not very focused on use and space planning, that there is uncertainty about structural condition and limited adaptation flexibility.</p>	<p>1 respondent said that there is always an important degree of uncertainty about the condition of the structure in terms of structural integrity - when referring to site visit/structural tests.</p>	

Condition survey and technical documentation

Step	Guideline/standard	Tool (software etc.)	When
Condition survey and technical documentation (4 respondents)	<p>1 respondent indicated that technical documentation is often poor or non-existent.</p> <p>2 respondents mentioned construction legislation/standards at national level.</p> <p>2 respondents mentioned heritage conservation standards at international level. 1 respondent mentioned heritage conservation standards at national level.</p>	<p>1 respondent is not aware of any condition survey tools.</p> <p>There was a consensus amongst 3 respondents (2 in Spain and 1 in Poland) about the task to carry out a building pathology analysis (ie understanding damages to masonry, wooden elements, etc.). No specific tool was mentioned.</p> <p>1 respondent mentioned the task to analyse the resistance of the building's structural elements (bearing walls, domes, etc) and the task of carrying out a historic analysis of the building. In both cases, no specific tool was mentioned.</p> <p>1 respondent mentioned the tools for the collection of 2D/3D technical information (e.g. Photogrammetry, 3D scanning).</p> <p>2 respondents (Spain and Poland) mentioned the processing of 2D/3D technical information (e.g. FARO PhoToPlan, BIM, photogrammetry tools</p>	<p>Consensus on timing amongst 3 respondents (2 in Spain and 1 in Poland) that this step should take place at the beginning of the retrofit process but diverging view on the specific point in time (either at pre-design stage or at the start of the design phase or during the stage when a light touch design is being informed).</p> <p>1 respondent also mentioned that this the heritage value assessment should also take place happening at a more advanced point in the design - i.e. the building permit stage (when a planning permission/listed building consent is sought from a city council or local authority).</p>

		within AutoCAD)	
Pros/cons	<p>2 respondents (Poland and Spain) found that there were detailed criteria provided by existing guidelines/standards (presumably heritage conservation standards at national/international level).</p> <p>However, one respondent felt that the legislation/standards do not work as a specific guide for any kind of building.</p> <p>1 respondent felt that up-to-date technical documentation of the buildings is often not available.</p>	<p>2 respondents (Spain and Poland) considered that the tools for the collection of 2D/3D technical information (e.g. Photogrammetry, 3D scanning) and for the processing of 2D/3D technical information (e.g. Photogrammetry, 3D scanning and BIM), as well as the task to carry out a building pathology survey, provide precise documentation on the current condition of the building. However, the 2 respondents found that there was a lack of information about internal structure (building pathology survey). 1 respondent also found that the tools are expensive (Photogrammetry, 3D scanning and BIM).</p> <p>1 respondent considered the tasks of undertaking building pathology and structural surveys to be indispensable.</p>	

Energy performance assessment

Step	Guideline/standard	Tool (software etc.)	When
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<p>Energy performance assessment <i>(5 respondents)</i></p>	<p>Strong consensus on the use, for energy performance assessment, of energy performance legislation for buildings at European level (EPBD), energy performance legislation/standards for buildings at national level and of energy performance standards (non-governmental) for buildings at national level (3 respondents respectively).</p> <p>Energy performance standards (non-governmental) for buildings at international level and construction legislation/standards at national level were also mentioned (2 respondents respectively).</p>	<p>A lot of tools were mentioned, and they can be split between those being compulsory or recognised by national governments to produce EPCs or required for energy modelling calculations, those who are not compulsory but are widely used and in-house tools.</p> <p>The most frequently mentioned tools (by 4 respondents (2 in Spain, 1 in the UK and 1 in Poland) are the software programs for energy modelling that are compulsory at national level or recognised by governments (e.g. Herramienta Unificada LIDER-CALENER (HULC), CE3X and CE3 in Spain, SPA/RdSAP in UK, ArCADia-TERMO and BuildDesk in Poland).</p> <p>3 respondents (Spain, UK and Poland) mentioned the tools (software) for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - energy modelling incl. Dynamic Simulation Modelling (software) that are non-obligatory (e.g. Audytor OZC, TRNSYS, PHPP, DesignBuilder EnergyPlus) - hygrothermal risk assessment - 	<p>General consensus on timing amongst 4 respondents (2 in Spain 1 in UK and 1 in Poland) that this step should take place at a more developed design stage or building permit stage.</p> <p>1 respondent also mentioned that this step should happen at several design stages, to check the performance of the design.</p> <p>1 respondent also mentioned that this step should also happen after completion of the project.</p>
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		<p>condensation in walls, roofs, ground floors (e.g. WUFI, BuildDesk)</p> <p>Tool (software) for thermal bridges modelling were mentioned by 2 respondents (Spain and UK).</p> <p>Various tools(software) were mentioned by 1 respondent to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - model heat fluxes through buildings components, thermal load and temperature and relative humidity evolution. Note: these can be covered by energy model software - calculate U-values (e.g. BuildDesk) <p>1 respondent mentioned the combination of tools (software) to generate 3D models and to assign energy performance values to the walls, roof, floor (Design PH platform which plugs into SketchUp).</p> <p>1 respondent mentioned an in-house tool to report on current energy performance of a building.</p>	
Pros/cons	The feedback is quite diverse and	The feedback was extremely diverse and tends to be specific to the various tools	

	<p>touched on various aspects.</p> <p>There is a feeling that there are very well-defined standards, detailed guidelines and that there are clear targets, and some flexibility on how some standards can be used (i.e. following the steps but not necessarily the specific targets).</p> <p>There was a consensus that the main challenge is complexity: complexity of the standards/legislations themselves, an increasing complexity due to the large numbers of standards/legislation that can generate contradictions between each other (a suggestion was made to group them in one single standard/guideline), the fact that different procedures are required depending on the standards/tools being used, and the difficulty in applying the standards to historic buildings.</p>	<p>used. However, some general conclusions can be made: there are a large number of tools available for energy performance assessment and they cover various aspects (some more integrated such Dynamic Simulation Modelling and some focusing on specific aspects such as hygrothermal risk assessment).</p> <p>The fact that the tools are easy to use (e.g. when based on Excel like PHPP) and provide results quickly is a strong advantage, whilst the fact that a tool is very time-consuming, requires skills and is slow to operate is problematic. Precision is very important and so is the ability to generate a lot of data that can be reused during the design process - whilst some tools can provide results that are not precise. Some tools are more focused on compliance with regulations (mandatory as part of national legislations) and there may be the need to use different tools - in which case, it is important that the interface between different tools is easy, as well as the possibility to use the data from one to another is important. It appears important</p>	
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		<p>that the tool is flexible and can allow comparison between different retrofit scenarios to test them and facilitate data interpretation - it was mentioned that this is an iterative process which needs optimising (e.g. using AI), because it is very time consuming, and that some software programs are not designed to enable an iterative process. Some software programs do not cover all design options. Some software programs lack data (e.g. climate data).</p> <p>One respondent highlighted these tools are indispensable, but the existing tools have their limitations. A well-designed monitoring campaign is absolutely necessary to calibrate and validate the energy models. Otherwise, their results are not reliable.</p>	
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Indoor environmental assessment

Step	Guideline/standard	Tool (software etc.)	When
Indoor environmental	2 respondents mentioned energy performance of buildings legislation/standards at national level	The feedback was generally diverse. 3 respondents (2 in Spain and 1 in	No consensus on timing amongst 4 respondents (2 in Spain 1 in UK and 1 in Poland) as to when this step should take

<p>assessment (5 respondents)</p>	<p>(Spain - RITE that stands for regulation on indoor heating and air-conditioning systems).</p> <p>2 respondents (Spain and Poland) mentioned indoor air quality in buildings standards (non-governmental) at national level.</p> <p>2 respondents (Spain and Poland) mentioned construction legislation/standards at national level</p> <p>Ad hoc approach/outsourced service to specialists and conservation guidelines were also mentioned.</p>	<p>Poland) mentioned tools for indoor environmental assessment (Verde 2022 Rev03, Design Builder (Energy Plus); WUFI; TRNSYS). These tools were already mentioned for energy performance assessment, and some are integrated energy modelling software programs.</p> <p>The following tools were mentioned by 1 respondent each:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tool for microclimate measurements/building performance monitoring (temperature, humidity and carbon dioxide) - Tool for multi-criteria certification - Tool to look at comfort levels/carry out thermal survey (thermal camera) <p>The following tasks were mentioned by 1 respondent each, but no tool was mentioned:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Task to carry out post occupancy evaluations (outsourced these reports to other companies) * Task to ask data from clients on 	<p>place. 2 respondents (Spain and UK) mentioned that this step should happen after completion of the project. 2 respondents (in Spain and in Poland) said that this step should take place at a more developed design stage or building permit stage. 1 respondent mentioned that this step should take place at the beginning of the retrofit process (at the start of the design phase).</p> <p>1 respondent also mentioned that this step could happen at several design stages - at the beginning of the retrofit process and after completion of the works.</p>
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		<p>operational parameters: energy use, temperature settings</p> <p>* Task to visit of the property and interviews with residents or building owners</p>	
<p>Pros/cons</p>	<p>2 respondents (Spain and Poland) found the standards/guidelines were clear.</p> <p>It was mentioned there was a comprehensive approach.</p> <p>However, there was a consensus that the main challenge is complexity: complexity of the standards/legislations themselves, increasing complexity due to the large numbers of standards/legislation that can generate contradictions between each other, and difficulty in achieving compromise between comfort and protection of historic buildings</p>	<p>The feedback collected was diverse and was either specific to the various tools used or more general.</p> <p>1 respondent mentioned that there is always uncertainty in the results of these parameters associated with indoor environmental assessment due to the actual use/occupancy of the building once it is retrofitted.</p> <p>1 respondent indicated that these tools provide data for other assessments (e.g. Wufi for hygrothermal risk).</p> <p>1 respondent in Spain indicated that Verde 2022 Rev03 is a very useful tool for technical staff and also for general public, such as future buyers without specific knowledge in architecture, but that it is also complex to implement.</p>	

Economic viability (e.g. Life cycle costing)

Step	Guideline/standard	Tool (software etc.)	When
<p>Economic viability <i>(5 respondents)</i></p>	<p>3 respondents mentioned they do not use or do not know the guidelines/standards for economic viability.</p> <p>2 other respondents (Spain and Poland) mentioned professional guidelines on economic viability - and one of the two respondents mentioned standards (non-governmental) at national/international level and National Grant Program Guidelines.</p>	<p>There seem to be 3 approaches on the assessment of the economic viability of a project: using a dedicated software or using an inhouse tool or analysing basic data on running costs.</p> <p>2 respondents (Spain and Poland) mentioned cost management software (e.g. Presto, Norma PRO, Zuzia,/BIMestiMate,BLCC Building Life Cycle Cost Program) that may have variations - they can or cannot be integrated with BIM and can or cannot include LCC calculations.</p> <p>1 respondent mentioned the task to analyse running costs and said that he was not using LCC tools.</p> <p>1 respondent mentioned custom LCC Excel formulas.</p>	<p>No consensus on timing amongst 3 respondents (1 in Spain 1 in UK and 1 in Poland) as to when this step should take place. 1 respondent mentioned that this step should take place during the stage when a light-touch design is being informed. 1 respondent mentioned that this step should take place at a more developed design stage and at the tender stage. 1 respondent mentioned that this step should at each stage when a cost is presented to the client.</p>
<p>Pros/cons</p>	<p>The feedback given by the 2 respondents aware of guidelines/standards for economic viability was diverse.</p> <p>In terms of benefits, existing guidelines/standards can be helpful to</p>	<p>The feedback collected was diverse and was more linked to specific tools.</p> <p>1 respondent made the general comment that he is not using LCC because they spend a lot of time trying to guess –</p>	

	<p>obtain a general preview of the economic balance, get clear cost structure, enable comparisons, the</p> <p>consideration of full building life cycle and a basis for long-term decision making.</p> <p>In terms of challenges, there were two categories of issues.</p> <p>Issues related to historic buildings/conservation works: difficulty in estimating conservation works and complexity of calculations for heritage buildings.</p> <p>And issues about the difficulty to estimate/anticipate construction costs in general: market price volatility, uncertainty of long-term economic forecasts and guidelines/standards does not reflect the current status of the construction market</p>	<p>“about how much do you think it's going to cost to replace this massive piece of ventilation kit in 15 years” time? And they feel that “they don't know.”</p> <p>1 respondent said that the software Presto is clear and simple, yet Presto is not very intuitive</p> <p>1 respondent saw an issue in that ZUZIA is not officially required by any institution in Poland.</p>	
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Environmental impact (e.g. Life cycle assessment, waste)

Step	Guideline/standard	Tool (software etc.)	When
Environmental	The feedback given by respondents was	The feedback collected was diverse due	General consensus on timing amongst 3

<p>impact (4 respondents)</p>	<p>diverse. There is no clear consensus on guidelines/standards for environmental impact.</p> <p>1 respondent did not use any guidelines/standards for environmental impact.</p> <p>Guidelines/standards for environmental impact that were mentioned include construction legislation/standards at national level, energy performance of buildings legislation/standards at national level, environmental legislation at national level, environmental standards (non-governmental) at national level and internal procedures.</p>	<p>to the diversity of aspects of environmental impact that tools could help with and showcased different tools/approaches.</p> <p>1 respondent mentioned a software for Environmental impact (e.g. Verde 2022 Rev03).</p> <p>2 respondents mentioned Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) software (e.g. SimaPro, OneClick). A 3rd respondent mentioned that they are using an in-house tool that could be inhouse or commercial tools. The in-house tool is a software to compare retrofit interventions/packages by mapping projected carbon reduction over a 60-year lifespan of a building and is primarily focused on operational energy rather than embodied carbon.</p> <p>1 respondent said they do not do pre demolition audits.</p> <p>1 respondent said they do not don't use them.</p>	<p>respondents (1 in Spain 1 in UK and 1 in Poland) that this step should take place at a more developed design stage or building permit stage.</p>
<p>Pros/cons</p>	<p>Only one respondent gave feedback on this - although this was not requested in</p>	<p>The feedback collected was diverse - although no feedback on pros/cons was</p>	

	<p>the form used.</p> <p>In terms of benefits, existing guidelines/standards can be helpful to grow environmental awareness.</p> <p>In terms of challenges, there is a high cost associated with the conducting of these analyses, a lack of specific guidelines for heritage buildings.</p>	<p>required for environmental impact tools.</p> <p>1 respondent said that there are tools available.</p> <p>However, 1 respondent said that there is a lack of reliable databases of materials and products, and that this is a big issue with LCA evaluations.</p> <p>1 respondent said they are currently upskilling in whole life carbon assessment (being more focused on the cradle to gate, i.e. the A modules of whole life assessment, and on operational energy).</p>	
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Tailored intervention solutions for future-proofing historic buildings

At FuturHist, we research and test energy-efficient retrofit interventions tailored to historic building typologies. We implement these solutions in real-life demonstration cases in Poland, Spain, Sweden and the UK. We focus on innovative solutions such as bio-based materials, internal insulation systems, window retrofits, HVAC, and RES integration.

DURATION OF THE PROJECT: JANUARY 2024-DECEMBER 2027

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